

MAKERERE **UNIVERSITY**

**ANALYSING CONSUMER PREFERENCES FOR QUALITY
CHARACTERISTICS OF SORGHUM GRAIN: A STUDY IN
TESO SUB-REGION OF UGANDA**

BY

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APPROVAL

I, Kakuru Kit Medard, hereby declare that to the best of my knowledge and understanding the work contained in this report is original and that it has never been submitted in part or wholly to Makerere University or any other institution of higher learning for the award of a degree. However, any sources of information are duly acknowledged.

Signed

Date

This thesis is submitted with our approval as University supervisors

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DEDICATION

Jesus, I dedicate this work to you, for you miraculously enabled me to be sponsored for my studies. You deserve the Glory! Secondly, I dedicate this work to my rib, Sarah and our daughter Elizabeth who missed me during my busy class schedules. Lastly, I dedicate this work to our late son Jedidiah, who was born during my examination period but later passed away without me carrying him. May his soul rest in eternal peace.

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

CA	Conjoint Analysis
CE	Choice experiment
CS	Compensating Surplus
CV	Contingent Valuation
ML	Mixed Logit
MNL	Multinomial Logit
MNCL	Multinomial conditional Logit
NBL	Nile breweries limited
RPL	Random Parameters Logit
RUT	Random Utility theory
SCM	Stated choice methods
WTP	Willingness to pay

ABSTRACT

Sorghum is an important staple cereal crop in Eastern Uganda and Uganda as a whole. Studies have been done about producer preferences for sorghum attributes but no work had been done on consumer preferences, hence need for such a study. The objectives of the study included determining the sorghum attributes that consumers prefer, determining the Willingness to pay for the attributes, and analyzing the effect of consumer characteristics on the willingness to pay for the attributes. A choice experiment survey design was used to collect data from 150 consumers in Soroti, Kumi and Bukedea district. The empirical work employed the mixed logit model to determine the attributes that consumers prefer. Individual specific willing to pay estimates were obtained after estimating the Mixed Logit model and used as a dependent variable in the analysis of the effect of consumer characteristics on the WTP for the quality attributes. The results of the mixed logit model revealed that elastic texture (p-value = 0.0005) and good smell (p-value = 0.0000) strongly influenced the preference and hence the utility function of the consumer. White colour was more preferred than other colours, which is inconsistent with reality from the interviews. According to key informants, the red and brown sorghum are preferred because they are associated with elastic texture and good smell. Thus, colour could have been suppressed by texture and smell in the estimation, especially since the evaluation was conducted on the combined attributes. On the basis of willingness to pay, the ranking of preference was: good smell UGX 1433); extensible/elastic texture (UGX 1098); white colour (UGX 1067); brown colour (UGX 915); cream colour (UGX 829) and good/sweet taste (UGX 703). The compensating surplus estimates for all hypothetical varieties were positive suggesting that generally consumers prefer a change from the current varieties. Socioeconomic characteristics (like education, age, income level, gender, household size) were also found to have an effect on the willingness to pay for sorghum attributes. From this study, it can be deduced that smell of *atap* and elastic texture influence consumers' preference most. Therefore, breeders should consider texture and smell of *atap* as key attributes during sorghum improvement. Consumer socioeconomic characteristics affected willingness to pay for attributes differently. It is recommended that deliberate measures be taken to develop and or disseminate varieties with attributes that consumers are willing to pay for. Further research is needed to evaluate sorghum grain colours alone to establish the colour that is most preferred.

CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

Sorghum (*Sorghum Bicolor*) is ranked fifth in world cereal crop production and utilization, after wheat, rice, maize and barley (Nangoti *et al.*, 2004). Global production of sorghum is estimated at 57.6 million tons (FAOSTAT 2004). The United States (US) is the world's largest producer of grain sorghum followed by India, Nigeria, Sudan, Ethiopia and Mexico (FAO, 2008; FAO, 2010; & FAS, 2013). U.S. grain sorghum production in 2012 totaled 5.4 million tonnes (NASS 2013). Currently most human consumption of sorghum occurs in low-income countries, while high-income countries typically use sorghum as a component in livestock feed or to produce ethanol (AKintayo & Sedgo, 2001; FAS, 2013). For instance, about 50 percent of sorghum is consumed by humans globally, but in the United States over 90 percent of the sorghum consumed is used as a component in livestock feed (FAS, 2013).

In Africa, sorghum is one of the major cereal grains for human consumption (United States Grain Council, 2008). The continent produces about 20 million tons of sorghum per annum, about one-third of the world crop (FAO, 2003). It has been cultivated for more than five thousand years and represents the main carbohydrate source for at least 20 million people (Rami *et al.*, 1998). For some impoverished communities in Africa, sorghum remains a principal source of energy, protein, vitamins and minerals (FAO, 1995). In Africa, human consumption accounts for almost three-quarters of total utilization and sorghum represents a large portion of the total calorie intake in many countries (FAO, 2013). It is well adapted to a wide range of ecological conditions and is able to produce good yields under dry conditions unfavourable to other cereals. It is uniquely adapted to Africa's climate, being both drought resistant and able to withstand periods of water-logging (Taylor, 2003). Because of its adaptability, sorghum plays a significant role in fighting hunger and food insecurity (USAID,

2010). In future, use of sorghum may increase as farmers replace maize with the drought-resistant crop in areas where rainfall is expected to decline due to climate change (Taylor, 2003).

Sub Saharan Africa (SSA) annually produces about 18 million metric tons of sorghum (FAO, 2003). Sorghum is the second most important cereal (after maize) in SSA (FAO, 2011). In Uganda, sorghum is the third most important staple cereal food crop following maize and rice (House 1995, Nambuya 2007). Production of sorghum in Uganda was estimated at 400,000 metric tons and domestic consumption stands at 375 metric tons in 2013 (FAO 2013). There has been a gradual increase in the area planted from 285 ha to 321ha, and this increase has been attributed to increasing consumption of sorghum in the brewing industry (USAID, 2010). Sorghum is primarily grown as a subsistence food crop in Uganda and less than 10% of annual production is commercially processed by industry. Sorghum is largely produced by small-holder farmers with farm yields of only 867kg/hectare on average. This is about 17% of the potential yield. Sorghum has been prioritized as a crop that can deliver development solutions and the 6% agricultural GDP needed to stem hunger and poverty among rural communities who thrive on small scale agriculture (Omamo *et al.*, 2006).

In Uganda, a large amount of sorghum is predominantly grown in Northern and Eastern Uganda where most of it is consumed as food (USAID, 2010). It is a commercial and a staple food crop for over 95% households in Eastern Uganda (Nabimba *et al.*, 2005). Sorghum is used as a principal grain for human diets and includes a variety of different sorghum products such as bread, sorghum beer, popped sorghum, beverages and porridge (Kayode *et al.*, 2005; Laura *et al.*, 2012). In Kabale, south-western Uganda, sorghum grains are mainly used in the production of several traditional alcoholic beverages such as kwete, omuramba, and tonto, in addition to Bushera (Muyanja *et al.*, 2003). Bushera is the most common traditional

fermented beverage produced in South-western Uganda. It is mainly prepared from sorghum grains which may be germinated or non-germinated. Bushera is produced at household level by spontaneous fermentation. It is consumed by all age groups, and is used both as a weaning food and a thirst quenching drink in the households and in Bushera bars.

Sorghum has also become an important cash crop as it is used as a raw material in the industrial production of clear beer, known as Eagle Lager (Elepu and Nalukenge, 2006). It is also a source of starch in the brewing of beer, and a source of malt in the production of non-alcoholic malt drinks. In the competitive environment of multinational enterprises, sorghum has been proven to be the best alternative to barley for lager beer brewing (FAS, 2013).

Although sorghum is better adapted to drier areas than maize, farmer adoption rates for sorghum varieties are always lower than that of maize (Mafuru, 2007). In addition, maize based food is more acceptable to urban consumers than sorghum based foods. Use of sorghum in food industry is very little, in spite of its greater availability, low price and comparatively good nutritional value. The amount of sorghum marketed is small because larger portions of sorghum produced are consumed in rural areas. Urban consumers generally have less preference to sorghum food. Virtually, all production is undertaken for subsistence purposes, with less than 2% of each season's harvest entering formal market (Rohrbach & Kiriwagulu, 2001). Presently, sorghum is 90% traded in the informal rural markets with only 10% or less being sold commercially to brewing industries to make opaque beer (Babatunde, 2001). This status quo is mainly due to the fact that the current varieties (both traditional and improved) are not suitable for prevailing market opportunities. According to Desikachar (1974) sorghum has remained food for lower income sections partly due to some constraints that limit its acceptability. The current traditional grain varieties can only satisfy the rural consumers. Because of the limited use of the current sorghum varieties, market

potentials remain unexploited. For instance, sweet sorghum is continuously being imported to make syrups because it has not been produced locally. Various interventions like introducing improved varieties have been undertaken, but have mostly focused on production-related issues. Demand-related traits have more or less not been incorporated into the new improved varieties, leaving sorghum unacceptable in the market chain. The poor marketability of sorghum has resulted into perpetual low prices of sorghum grain. Prices of sorghum are often discounted compared with those of maize (Rohrbach, 2003). The key to increasing marketability of sorghum is by offering varieties with acceptable traits in the market (Wilson & Dahl, 1999). Given that several products with different quality characteristics can be obtained from sorghum (Tiisekwa & Laswai, 1993), there is need to direct much of the research effort (breeding programs) towards the desired consumer characteristics. These characteristics are important because they have a bearing on acceptability. Therefore, this study was conducted to determine and evaluate sorghum grain attributes that consumers consider while buying it for food.

1.2 Problem statement

Given the economic, environmental adaptation and social importance of sorghum, its production strategy is worth undertaking to eradicate food insecurity, generate household income and hence poverty reduction in Eastern Uganda. Besides its traditional use as a food crop, sorghum has alternative uses such as livestock and poultry feed, potable alcohol, starch and ethanol production (Kleih *et al.*, 2000). Commercialising agriculture is viewed globally, and Uganda in particular, as the way to go in order to promote rural development. Many interventions have been undertaken to promote commercialisation, including development of high yielding, drought tolerant varieties; free distribution/ or subsidisation of inputs like seeds. However, many smallholder farmers have not been able to exploit the potential gains

from commercialization due to limited utilization base of sorghum food. The current varieties do not meet the desires of various chain actors/end-users (Kayode *et al.*, 2005). Varietal development has been supply-driven rather than demand-driven. Past research gave inadequate attention to the quality of the varieties as perceived by consumers of sorghum products (Mafuru *et al.*, 2007). The breeding programs never incorporated desirable consumption attributes and non-yield production traits into new varieties (Dalton, 2004). Variety development has primarily been directed towards improving agronomic characteristics (high yield, tolerance to drought/pests/weeds) (Badu-Apraku *et al.*, 1995; Tenywa *et al.*, 1999). However, the strategy of increasing yields without concomitant strategies to increase market penetration cannot fully exploit the potential that lies in agriculture. Over 10 improved varieties of sorghum have been developed, but few of these varieties have been adopted (Kayode *et al.*, 2005). According to Koudokpun (1991), only 12 % of the area cultivated is devoted to new cultivars in spite of their favourable agronomic characteristics. Nago (1997) asserts that the inability of the new varieties to meet consumers' quality expectations was identified as the major obstacle to adoption by users. Adoption of new technology depends on both product characteristics and market opportunities of the product (Anon, 1989). Demand for a variety is influenced by consumers' demand from food markets and farmers' consumption requirements (Mafuru *et al.*, 2007). Therefore, a new product should be able to meet the needs, tastes and preferences of the target consumers (Keane & Willets 1994).

When crossing varieties with particular traits, scientists should attempt to consider consumer characteristics/preferences such as taste, cooking qualities, colour and appearance. Varietal development and promotion should include consumption characteristics in addition to production traits when determining which varieties to promote for official release (Dalton 2004). These characteristics are important because they have a bearing on acceptability of

new products (Kimenju *et al.*, 2005). Grunert, (2002) consider product traits/attributes as one of the perspectives to increase understanding of consumer choice. Kayode *et al.*, (2005) also argue that the quality of the food product which results from the grain determines the choice of the sorghum variety by the processors.

Research on seed supply constraints has been done but variety-specific demand constraints have not been thoroughly researched. The efforts to develop improved cultivars with built in quality for processing are critically important for successful utilisation and increased profits for farmers as well (Rooney, 1997). Demand for varieties is a function of grain and the attributes preferred by consumers that are embodied in the varieties (Ndjeunga & Nelson, 2005). Therefore, consumer quality characteristics should be carefully studied and be provided for in any product offering. This study was conducted to identify and evaluate sorghum characteristics/attributes that consumers base on to make choice of grain variety. It is envisaged that once important attributes have been identified and willingness to pay for those attributes is elicited, breeders will be in position to come up with market-specific varieties, hence increasing marketability of sorghum.

1.3 Objectives of the study

The overall objective of the study was to analyse consumer preferences for sorghum grain attributes in Uganda.

1.3.1 Specific objectives

- i. To establish grain attributes that influence consumption of sorghum grain.
- ii. To determine the willingness to pay by consumers for sorghum grain attributes.
- iii. To determine the effect of consumer characteristics on the Willingness to pay (henceforth WTP) for sorghum grain attributes.

1.4 Hypotheses

1. Sorghum grain attributes significantly influence consumers' preference.
2. There is a contribution to price that consumers are willing to pay for the quality attributes.
3. Socio-economic characteristics of sorghum grain consumers significantly influence consumers' WTP for quality attributes.

1.5 Justification for the study

One of the most recurrent complaints by government in peasant societies is that farmers are not responsive to price incentives and to opportunities to adopt new technologies for cash crop production (Alain et al., 1991). This is partly so because the products available on the market are not desirable for consumers. This has resulted into frustrated policies of incentives and modernisation. Such a study will help elicit the important quality characteristics as perceived by consumers, and hence promote marketability.

In the academic field, this study will add knowledge in understanding how preferences for product attributes vary across individuals. Most studies on preferences never provided for the possibility that individuals make decisions under different conditions/circumstances. This study is not only going to establish the attributes that consumers like but it will also attempt to establish whether there are differences in preferences among consumers. This study will however not look at sources of those differences.

1.6 Scope

The study covered three districts in Teso region. These are: Soroti, Bukedea, and Kumi. The study was specifically conducted in this region because per capita consumption of sorghum in Uganda is highest in Eastern and North-Eastern regions (USAID, 2010). The study involved

households in the sorghum farming population but these were treated as consumers of sorghum. The study strictly covered consumer attributes only. One sub-county and a weekly market were involved in each district. The study also attempted to discover whether there were differences in preferences across individuals but never looked at the source of those differences. The study however, established whether consumption behavior and preference patterns varied among the consumers in the three districts. The study was conducted in period of March 2013 up to May2013. Sorghum grain could be consumed in many forms including porridge, bread or brew and each of these products has its own quality preferences. However, for the purposes of this study, the preferences being elicited are those of sorghum bread (atapa).

CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW

This chapter covers the theoretical perspectives and empirical evidence of consumers' preferences and willingness to pay in the context of quality characteristics of sorghum.

2.1 Theoretical framework

Sorghum based food products are not performing well on the market compared to their cereal counterparts like maize and wheat. Prices of sorghum are often discounted compared with those of maize (Rohrbach, 2003). This is due to the fact that the current varieties have less desirable consumer attributes (Figure 1). This has led to poor marketability of sorghum grain and its food products. At the same time the undesirable attributes of sorghum have led to a negative attitude towards sorghum products, which further aggravates its marketability. This calls for market/consumer-oriented research and breeding programs. Consumer-oriented research will facilitate elicitation of consumer tastes and preferences for the product while breeding will ensure that varieties developed satisfy consumer tastes and preferences. Research will also help to identify consumer demographic characteristics that influence attitude and preference towards a product. This is so because the decision to buy and consume a product depends on both the product and consumer (socioeconomic) characteristics (Steenkamp et al., 1996). Socioeconomic characteristics along with product attributes shape a consumer's WTP, because those characteristics affect attitudes towards the product (Ulimwengu & Prabuddha, 2001).

Socioeconomic variables such as age, gender, education level, location and income are important in explaining consumer demand for food (Gracia & Tiziana, 2007). For instance, income positively influences preference and hence willingness to pay for food products (Torjusen *et al.*, 2001; Kuhar & Juvancic, 2005). Age and education level of the consumer

also significantly increase the probability of being a heavy consumer of some food products (Millock *et al.*, 2004). Furthermore, consumption patterns for rural consumers and urban consumers are different and the differences are due to their socio-economic environments (Mafuru *et al.*, 2007). For a product like sorghum, urban consumers have less preference for it compared to rural consumers. This explains why sorghum is primarily used as livestock feed in developed countries, whereas it is a staple food crop in impoverished communities.

‘Private good’ attributes have also been found to motivate purchase decisions for foods. According to Moskiwitz *et al.*, (2004), purchase decisions are usually made depending on the evaluation of several product characteristics (observable and unobservable), with some attributes carrying more value than others. Product characteristics/attributes can be intrinsic or extrinsic. Intrinsic cues that influence consumers’ attitude and hence WTP include appearance, texture, taste, colour, size, freshness and smell. Consumers will frequently value similar packages of foods differently based on subtle differences in the attributes of those foods (Melton *et al.*, 1996). For instance, there is a universal consumer preference for white- and cream-coloured sorghum products (Rooney & Murty, 1982a). Sorghum varieties which produce white or khaki flour have a high palatability and hence a high chance of being accepted by sorghum consumers (Mafuru *et al.*, 2007). For malting purposes, however, grains possessing a bright red colour are sold at premium prices (Murty, 1992).

Some extrinsic attributes of food products such as price, brand name, familiarity, health and nutritional benefits have been used to influence perceived product quality, intention to purchase and select products for consumers (Deliza & MacFie, 1996). For instance, price is particularly important to consumers of sorghum foods (Mafuru *et al.*, 2007) because sorghum has substitutes and any price increment will reduce demand and hence consumption of

sorghum food products. Furthermore, consumers purchase sorghum food products based on their health properties (Deliza & MacFie, 1996). Consumers consider grain products as “healthy food”, “cheap”, and “convenient”. Sorghum is believed to include low content of sugar, fat, sodium and calories; high protein and fiber content. In addition, sorghum is gluten-free and therefore considered safe for people with celiac diseases (Ciacci *et al.*, 2007). Nutritional aspects of the food product also influence consumer preference and willingness to pay. For instance, brown, high-tannin, bird-resistant sorghums contain condensed tannins (Murty, 1992) and such would be less consumed to the consumer whose ultimate intention is to get protein from it. The tannins have protein-binding capacity, which reduces protein bio-availability. Sorghums without pigmented testa do not contain condensed tannins and have acceptable value (Murty, 1992).

Figure 1: Framework of factors which influence consumer preference and WTP

2.2 Theoretical perspectives and empirical studies on consumer preferences and willingness to pay

A consumer is assumed to make a choice from amongst available alternatives in such a way that the level of satisfaction derived from consuming a commodity is highest (Henderson & Quandt, 1980). According to Grunert *et al.*, (1996), product attributes are one of the perspectives that influence consumer preference for a product. A product is therefore constituted by several characteristics and components referred to as product attributes, and these are what buyers base on to make their choices. These attributes could be classified as intrinsic or extrinsic (Grunert *et al.*, 1996).

Intrinsic attributes refer to inherent sensory qualities of the product like the appearance, colour, freshness taste, and smell. The sensory appeal of a product is a powerful influence on consumer acceptability (Cardello, 1994). In a study conducted by Dinis *et al.*, (2011) to determine consumers' acceptance for traditional apple varieties, it was found out that intrinsic characteristics of apples (appearance, texture, taste and smell) had strong significant influence on consumer choice. The study revealed that consumers preferred apples with better taste, appearance and smell (aroma). In another study to evaluate the sensory characteristics of the cheeses using 32 aroma, flavour, texture and appearance attributes, consumer preference for vintage cheese was influenced by its strong "salty" and "acidic" flavour (Murray & Delahunty, 2000). In addition, consumers preferred the vegetarian cheese to vintage and Farmhouse cheese and were influenced by its "moist" and "smooth" texture, "shiny" appearance and slightly "processed" flavour. Furthermore, a study to investigate food vendor and consumer preferences regarding fresh and prepared vegetables revealed that fresh appearance of tomatoes had a significant positive effect on consumer preference because appearance underlines the key role for assessing the quality of vegetables (Lorenz *et al.*, 2012). In the same study, the color attribute was significantly positive demonstrating that

consumers prefer ripe tomatoes. The results are consistent with results from Hugo & Kimenju (2008), who compared consumer preferences for colour and nutritional quality in maize. In the study, consumers showed a strong preference for white maize, whereas a price discount of 37% would be required to accept yellow maize. Meenakshi *et al.*, (2012) used a mixed logit (ML) model in the study to elicit the demand for a nutritious food in rural Zambia. Respondents made a choice of which of the three alternatives (orange, white and yellow maize) they would prefer to purchase based on the utility they derive from consuming the product. The results indicated that yellow maize varieties suffered a discount relative to white maize. Dinis *et al.*, (2011) conducted a survey to determine consumers' WTP for Portuguese traditional apple varieties. In the study, a hedonic price model was developed to explain how the price that consumers are WTP was related to apple appearance, taste and production method. The results indicated that consumers, regardless of their socio-economic characteristics, were willing to pay a higher price for apples with better taste, appearance and smell. Mafuru *et al.*, (2007) used a logistic model to determine preference ranking of different improved sorghum varieties and the results indicated that colour and taste of sorghum 'ugali' were the most important criteria used by consumers to evaluate the quality of 'ugali'. Ugali with white/khaki colour and neutral or slightly sweet taste were preferred.

Elements that influence the user from outside, such as product price, packaging, labeling/brand name as well as personal and situational variables are termed as extrinsic factors. For instance Price of a product is an extrinsic factor that influences consumers' preference for the product. Price has been reported to be an important factor affecting consumer perception such as purchase intent (Mafuru *et al.*, 2007). Consumer perception of the price alters one's choice in terms of amount to consume and its corresponding usage likelihood (Su-Huey & Tan, 2009). According to Boccaletti & Nardella (2000), price is a critical factor in determining the level of demand for pesticide-free Fresh Fruits and

Vegetables (FFV). A study conducted by Thompson & Kidwell (1998) on consumers' choices of organic and conventional produce in USA revealed that buying organic foods depends on price levels. In the study, consumers would be willing to buy more of organic produce at lower than at higher prices. This study is consistent with one done by Golnaz *et al.*, (2011) that analysed Malaysian consumers' perception towards purchasing organically produced vegetables. The study revealed that the price factor affects consumers' attitude towards purchasing organically grown vegetables. Nelson *et al.*, (2005) conducted a study in Haiti to evaluate consumer preferences for three attributes of roasted peanuts: form (dry-roasted vs. honey-roasted), country of origin (Haiti vs. USA), and price (lowest vs. most common vs. highest). The study revealed that price was the most important attribute. Price has also been reported to be an important factor affecting consumer WTP for sorghum grain and sorghum food products. In a study conducted by Mafuru *et al.*, (2007) to analyse consumer perception of sorghum variety attributes in the lake zone Tanzania, price influenced preferences of sorghum food products, and that price was particularly important to rural consumers than urban consumers.

Price premiums, the excess prices paid over and above the "fair" price that is justified by the "true" value of the product (Rao & Burgen, 1992), may be indicators of consumers' demand for that product (Tse, 2001). A study conducted by Kamal *et al.*, (2009) to analyse consumers' WTP for organic products in Kathmandu valley revealed that the willingness to pay price premium varied considerably. In the study, about 39% of the respondents felt the extra cost for organic products was reasonable, while 27% considered it too high. In a study by Jangu *et al.*, (2011) to demonstrate difference in willingness to pay between the informed test and the blind test of the 15 rice samples, consumers evaluated willingness to pay of rice samples more highly in the informed test than that in the blind test. Consumers evaluated WTP based on the price information provided in the informed test, whereas in the blind test,

they evaluated WTP of rice on the acceptance of rice samples. In another study to investigate WTP for renewable energy technologies in the UK, Ricardo & Willis (2010) found that much as households value renewable energy, the value was not significantly large to justify payment for renewable energy. Capital costs for micro-generation technologies were high but their value not worth payment.

Besides product price, another extrinsic factor that has been found to influence consumer preference for commodity is place or country of origin. Locality and origin of a product seem to be important attributes needed to differentiate and create new markets (Loureiro & Hine, 2001). According to Cordell (1992), consumers express preferences for products from countries over those of other countries. The origin preferences may reflect a positive home-country bias compared to similar countries (Chao, 1989) or reflect a negative home-country bias, if the home country is less developed than alternative sources (Tan & Farley, 1987). Jang *et al.*, (2011) studied consumer perception of rice samples from different countries of origin and found out that the palatability of rice from Japan was generally higher. Consequently consumer acceptance of rice from Japan was generally higher than that of rice from other countries. In addition, rice samples from Japan had relatively high head rice and low protein content, which also enhanced consumer preference for rice from Japan. Similarly, in a survey done by Nadezhda & Mazzocco (2008) to measure consumers' preference for apple attributes (place and method of production), place-oriented consumers demonstrated preference for locally grown apples. In another study conducted by Loureiro & Umberger (2004) to estimate WTP for country of origin labeling (COOL), respondents were willing to pay for a mandatory country-of-origin program. In the study, consumers were willing to pay more for steak and hamburger labeled as "U.S. certified steak" and "U.S. certified hamburger". This is also consistent with the findings by Schupp & Gillespie (2001b) that consumers supported and were willing to pay for mandatory country-of-origin labeling of

beef in grocery stores and restaurants. On the other hand, Loureiro & Umberger (2004) studied consumers' relative value of food safety, COOL, traceability and tenderness of two types of beef ribeye steaks that contain a number of attributes at different levels. A Multinomial conditional logit (MNCL) model was used to determine the consumers' probability of selecting the beef steak choice. The results indicated that country of origin labeling was not significant in selection of ribeye steaks while the rest of the choice specific attributes were statistically significant.

Consumers use place or country of origin to evaluate safety of the food product. Country of origin labeling (COOL) provides a traceability system that would increase food safety and consumer demand (Loureiro & Umberger, 2004) . Food safety concerns and threats of bioterrorism have played an important role in escalating consumer demand for source verification of food (Caswell, 1998). Consumers in the U.S have considered COOL of beef products to be an alternative that would enable consumers to choose U.S. produced beef (Brester & Smith, 1998) due to high food safety perceptions associated with U.S. beef. Similarly, in a study conducted by Roosen *et al.*, (2003), consumers in France and Germany indicated that the origin of their beef was more important than any other product attributes.

Much as food safety is evaluated based on place/country of origin, it is a concern to many consumers of food products regardless of the country of origin. Consumers are willing to pay for a value attached to the improvements of food safety (Henson, 1996). Consumer concerns about the potentially adverse effects of pesticide residues on human health have prompted some supermarket chains and food retailers to use private testing programs to advertise and promote their produce, while others have offered organically grown produce (OGP) (Misra *et al.*, 1991). Food safety concerns explain why consumers are willing to pay for organic certification (Lorenz *et al.*, 2012). Organic products are desired compared to eco-labeled products because organic products are perceived as safer due to their lower pesticide residues

(Loureiro *et al.*, 2001; Hansen *et al.*, 2002). Huang (1996) conducted a study to analyse consumer preferences and attitudes towards OGP and found out that consumers who are concerned about the use of pesticides and wanting produce tested for freedom from residues would have a higher propensity to prefer OGP to conventional produce. In another study to analyse consumer WTP for pesticide-free fresh fruit and vegetables (FFV) in Italy, Boccaletti & Nardella (2000) found out that Italian consumers were generally concerned about health risks from pesticides, with only 11% of the respondents not willing to pay higher for pesticide-free FFV. A Mixed Logit model was also used in the survey conducted to analyze the potential for marketing organic vegetable in the food vending sector to strengthen vegetable safety and revealed that consumers in Benin, Ghana and Burkina Faso were willing to pay a premium of 1.04 USD for organic certified vegetables (Lorenz *et al.*, 2012). Furthermore, Wang *et al.*, (2008) did a study of Chinese consumer demand for food safety attributes in milk products. They found out that nearly all respondents were willing to pay a modest price premium for Hazard Analysis Critical Control point (HACCP) - certified products. Products with HACCP labels in Beijing supermarkets sold at a price premium of about 5% over products without such labels, holding other attributes constant. HACCP is a quality management system used to reduce food safety risks.

There are other product attributes (perceived benefits) that are perceived to influence consumption and WTP for food products. These include health and nutritional benefits derived from consuming a product in question. Information about nutritional benefits can play a significant role in driving consumer acceptance. A study conducted by Meenakshi *et al.*, (2012) to elicit demand for three maize products (orange, white and yellow maize) revealed that nutrition campaigns translated into improved acceptance and WTP for orange maize. Huang (1996) assessed the factors affecting consumers' preference of pesticide free

fresh produce and found out that nutritional content of the produce had a positive significant effect on consumer choice. Colson & Huffman (2011) did a survey of consumers' willingness to pay for genetically modified foods with product-enhancing nutritional attributes and found out that consumers were willing to pay a premium for both intragenic and transgenic labels with enhanced vitamin C and antioxidant relative to a conventional plain label alternative. Kimenju *et al.*, (2005) did a similar study in Western Kenya using a double bound logistic model to find out how consumers balance the improved nutritional quality against the undesired colour change. They found out that yellow maize gets a premium in Siaya region and a discount in Vihiga. The perception about nutritional quality was however different according to the survey conducted by Hugo & Kimenju (2008) to compare consumers' preferences for colour and nutritional quality in maize. They compared white maize with yellow maize which was bio-fortified to enhance its nutritional quality. The results obtained showed that consumers had a strong preference for white maize. Only a minority would buy yellow maize at the same price as white maize. In sorghum, phytate and tannins are of particular concern to nutritionists because of their possible adverse effect on digestibility and bioavailability of minerals and proteins (Kayode *et al.*, 2005). Phytate forms insoluble complexes with essential minerals such as calcium, iron and zinc at physiological pH levels. This phytate is partially responsible for the widespread mineral deficiencies observed in populations that subsist largely on sorghum (Hulse *et al.*, 1980).

Health consciousness has been found to predict attitudes, intention and purchase of food products (Magnusson *et al.*, 2003). The matter of increased health care through proper nutrition is a key factor influencing consumption choice (Shuharudin *et al.*, 2010). Consumers consider health properties of sorghum important before purchasing sorghum food products. Sorghum does not contain gluten and is hydrolysed slowly, making it attractive to diabetics, celiac and ethnic groups (Rooney, 1997). Because of this feature, sorghum provides

a basis for gluten-free breads and other baked products like cakes and cookies/biscuits and for making snacks and pasta (Taylor *et al.*, 1996).

Economic literature indicates that consumer characteristics also affect consumer preferences due to their influence on consumer behavior (Baker & Mazzocco, 2005), and hence willingness to pay. In a study conducted by Kayode *et al.*, (2005), to investigate quality of consumers' varieties of sorghum in Benin, socio-economics factors were found to affect consumer preferences for sorghum grain. In the study, preference depends on sex and age. For instance, *kamanguia* (a porridge type in Benin) is mainly consumed by women, especially by nursing mothers because it is believed to stimulate lactation. In addition, older people argue that white sorghum bread causes diarrhoea, but justify their attachment to pink/red bread by its supposed richness in nutritious elements or its ability to provide iron which is an important ingredient for formation of blood.

The evaluation of quality of sorghum also depends on location of the consumer. Each country, and in some instances, even different areas within a country, has its own measure of quality (Graham., 1999). In a study done by Nadezhda & Mazzocco (2008) to analyze consumer preferences and trade-offs for locally grown and GM apples, linear regression model results revealed that place-oriented consumers were willing to pay 60 – 70% premiums for locally grown apples. In another study done by Kayode *et al.*, (2005), preference depended on ethnic group for some sorghum food products. For instance, in the *Bariba* community (ethnic group in Benin), the best gift to a young mother is a pot of *kamanguia*.

Consumer characteristics may directly influence willingness to pay (Bruhn 1995; Xia & Zeng 2008). In a study on willingness to purchase organic food, Carlos *et al.*, (2005) found out that women, youth, high income class and educated people were willing to pay a premium for a product perceived to have good quality characteristics. In another study conducted by

Loureiro & Hine (2001), the likelihood to purchase organic products and pay a premium increased with increase in income and education level. Fuat *et al.*, (2006) also found the same pattern in the influence of education level and income. In that survey, respondents with at least a high school degree and higher household income were more likely to pay a premium for organically farmed sea bass. However, in a study conducted by Misra *et al.*, (1991) respondents with a college education were less likely to be willing to pay more for certified-FPR produce. The findings obtained from a study conducted by Hugo & Kimenju (2008) revealed that income and education had a clear negative effect on the willingness to pay for yellow maize, and women had a lower WTP than men. Household size has also been found to have an effect on WTP. In a survey done by Loureiro *et al.*, (2001), family size had a significant negative effect on the willingness to pay for organic apples. In the survey, shoppers with large families were more likely to have an economizing mindset, inducing the purchase of low-cost items. . In addition, households with children are likely to prefer some products over others. For instance, Eco-labeled apples were found to be less desirable when compared with organic apples for consumption with children because organic products are perceived as safer for children due to lower pesticide residues (Loureiro *et al.*, 2001).

The evaluation of quality of sorghum also depends on location of the consumer. Each country, and in some instances, even different areas within a country, has its own measure of quality (Graham *et al.*, 1999). In a study done by Nadezhda & Mazzocco (2008) to analyze consumer preferences and trade-offs for locally grown and GM apples, linear regression model results revealed that place-oriented consumers were willing to pay 60 – 70% premiums for locally grown apples. In another study done by Kayode *et al.*, 2005, preference depended on ethnic group for some sorghum food products. For instance, in the *Bariba* community (ethnic group in Benin), the best gift to a young mother is a pot of *kamanguia*.

2.3 Review of approaches used to elicit Willingness to pay

Seraphine (2010) defined WTP as the amount of money that an individual is willing to sacrifice to acquire a good or service. The WTP function establishes the price that an individual is willing to pay for a given level of quality, given prices, income and preferences (Lusk & Hudson, 2004). WTP is an indicator of the value of the commodity to that individual. The link between product prices and product attributes/ characteristics was articulated by Rosen (1974). According to Rosen (1974), consumers value goods based on their utility-generating attributes, and that consumers assess product attributes/characteristics when making a purchase decision. Furthermore, the observed market price for the product is an aggregate of the implicit prices for the constituent product attributes/characteristics. Thus, product prices provide signals about the inherent quality characteristics of a product. The characteristics of goods can be substituted when relative prices change (Lancaster, 1966). A price premium paid for the attributes/characteristics suggests that consumers place a high value on such attributes (Bonti-Ankomah & Yiridoe, 2006). Furthermore, Lancaster (1966) argues that a good which does not possess all the characteristics a consumer desires cannot be a dominant good no matter how low its price, while a good that has characteristics not possessed by any other good cannot be inefficient no matter how high the price is.

There are a variety of ways to determine willingness-to-pay for a certain good or service. These techniques are commonly used to estimate the value that is placed on current market goods, non-market goods (such as hunting rights), as well as for determining a price for products or services that at the current time do not have a market value (like frozen aquatic sperm) (Boever, 2006). Economists and market researchers have used contingent valuation (CV), choice experiments (CEs) and experimental auctions (EA) or combinations of the three methods to elicit consumer preferences for products/services on various attributes (Loureiro & Umberger, 2005).

Experimental auctions (EA) are approaches whereby real transactions take place and participants bid with real money on real products (in this case sorghum grain). The highest bidder(s) win the auction and pay(s) a price that is determined exogenously from the individual's bid. Experimental auctions differ from contingent valuation not only in the framing of the task for the respondent, but also in whether real money is involved or not (Grunert *et al.*, 2009). Experimental auctions would be advantageous in that they create an active market environment with feedback where consumers exchange sorghum and real money, and exact willingness to pay measures are obtained. Auction outcomes are therefore considered closest to true WTP. Nevertheless, these auctions are more difficult to organise, and require more time and resources. EAs were also used in soliciting consumer preferences for maize in Kenya (Kimenju *et al.*, 2005), and actually produced the most realistic preference estimates compared to CV and CE methods.

Contingent Valuation Method (CVM) is an economic, non-market based valuation method normally used to predict individual preferences for public goods, notably environmental quality (Seraphine, 2010). CVM is mostly used in the absence of markets for public goods by providing the consumers with hypothetical market in which they have the opportunity to buy the good in question. Different methods are used to ask respondents to calculate the amount of money (bid level) they are willing to pay for a good when given a chance to acquire it. The elicitation methods include open –ended questions, the bidding game, the payment card, dichotomous choice questions and the randomized card sorting procedure (Engel, 2008). In our case, the consumer assigns a value to a sorghum variety, by facing a hypothetical purchasing situation in which they have to answer how much money or how much more they would be willing to pay for a given variety. The main limitation of CVM is the hypothetical predisposition which if based on information provided by the respondents, and in most cases the respondents often have incentive to strategically respond and to not tell the truth (Lusk &

Hudson, 2004). In addition, the contingent valuation method is inadequate to value single attributes of a multi-attribute good, such as the quality attributes embedded in a given variety. CVM was used by Hanemann (1984) in the study of welfare evaluations among the hunters. In this study, hunters were asked if they were willing to sell their permits for a specified sum of money and supposing they had not received their permits, if they were willing to pay a specified price to obtain them. This method was also used in soliciting consumer preferences for maize in western Kenya (Kimenju *et al.*, 2005).

Choice experiments (CEs) are based on Lancaster's theory of consumer choice which postulates that consumers choose products based on their attributes (Lancaster, 1966). CEs permit multiple attributes to be evaluated, thereby allowing the researcher to estimate trade-offs between different alternatives (Lusk *et al.*, 2003). Given that sorghum grain also has multiple attributes, it would be possible to evaluate the attributes using a CE. This technique assumes that the consumer derives separate amounts of utility provided by each attribute of a sorghum variety (Boever, 2006). The choice modeling approach attempts to understand the respondents' preferences over attributes of the scenario rather than a single specific scenario (Adamowicz *et al.*, 1998). In a CE modeling study, respondents could be provided alternative varieties and asked to choose which of the varieties they would purchase, given the attributes and descriptions of the competing varieties (Lusk & Hudson, 2004). Repeated choices by respondents from sets of alternatives reveal the trade-offs consumers are willing to make between characteristics/attributes and price, including wider variation in relevant variables than might be observed in actual field data. Hence, when individuals make their choice, they make trade-offs between attribute levels and cost/price. Statistical analyses of responses obtained from CEs can be used to derive the marginal values for attributes of a good. The marginal values are then used to generate preferences of consumers for existing or hypothetical products that are described in terms of the level of attributes. The overall

preference of a specific profile is obtained by adding up the estimated coefficients of the levels of attributes that make up the profiles. Econometric modeling of CEs assumes an additive utility function where the sum of partial utilities of each attribute is equal to the total utility (Kallas *et al.*, 2007). CVM differs from CE in that the former presents consumers with only one alternative at one price, while the latter presents consumers with a choice set that contains several alternatives that vary along several attributes, including price (Deshazo & German, 2002).

The choice modeling methodology has an edge over other methods by varying simultaneously several attributes of a product and estimating the marginal rates of substitution between these attributes, and especially the WTP for specified characteristics. It provides great flexibility in the sense that many different scenarios can be presented in a single study. Furthermore, choice modeling is not only easily adaptable to nonlinear relationships in the data, but also allows researchers to make separate predictions for the effects of each level of the independent variable and does not assume that they are related at all (Boever, 2006). It is also used in determining consumers' willingness-to-pay for products that embody certain characteristics or groups of characteristics (Hair, 1995). However, the choices made by consumers in hypothetical surveys might not reflect their real preferences. It has proven that participants in hypothetical surveys generally state higher WTP for a good, leading to the hypothetical bias (Murphy *et al.*, 2005). To overcome this redundant problem, choice experiments can be made incentive – compatible by linking participants' decisions to real consequences.

CEs have been applied to value the environmental attributes (Hanley *et al.*, 1998), elicit what farmers want from Agri-environment scheme design (Espinosa-Goded *et al.*, 2010), estimate willingness to pay for health policy evaluation (Carson & Louviere, 2010), study consumer preferences for roasted peanut products in Haiti (Nelson *et al.*, 2005), assess development

policy in Uganda (James, 2010), and to investigate household's willingness to pay for renewable energy technologies in the UK (Scarpa & Willis, 2010). A notable development is in the use of CEs to inform the design of policies or programmes (Ruto & Garrod, 2009; and Otieno *et al.*, 2011).

The hedonic price technique has also been widely used to estimate marginal values for product characteristics (Faminow & Gum, 1986). However, choice experiment is preferred because, preferences being measured directly, the results are less likely to be adversely affected by attributes that are not priced or transactions that do not occur through organized markets. The hedonic price is also inappropriate in circumstances where the market is unregulated and most households have no record about market transactions. Furthermore, some of the important non income (socio-cultural) functions of food products in Uganda are embedded in traits that are not traded in the market, therefore lacking price or market values (Ouma *et al.*, 2007). Hence, utilization of a hedonic price model would result in exclusion of attributes considered desirable for consumers. This calls for the employment of a valuation method that can also permit calculations of economic values of qualities without market values to be included in modeling process. In addition, the use of hedonics is limited to the valuation of existing traits and not prospective traits that may be of interest to consumers (Ouma *et al.*, 2007). CEs overcome this limitation since preferences are measured directly, and then related to utility, making it possible to estimate economic values of prospective qualities (Ouma *et al.*, 2007).

Given the limitations of the EAs, CVM and hedonic price techniques, this study used data collected through a CE survey of household grain consumers. The strength of this method lies in its ability to evaluate goods that consist of several attributes (Kallas *et al.*, 2007). In addition, because CEs are based on attributes, they allow the researcher to "value" attributes as well as situational changes (Adamowicz *et al.*, 1998).

CHAPTER THREE: METHODOLOGY

3.1 Description of study area

The study was conducted in Teso sub-region. Teso sub-region (previously known as Teso District) is a region in Uganda that consists of Amuria district, kaberamaido, Kumi, Katakwi, Bukedea, Ngora, Serere and Soroti district. The region is home to an estimated 2.5 million people of Iteso and Kumam ethnicities. The sub-region was purposively selected because sorghum bread (*atapa*) is the staple food in the region.

The sub-region experiences a humid and hot climate, receiving bimodal rainfall with an average between 1000 – 1350mm, much of which is received between March to May. The climate of the region is modified by the large swamp wetland area that surrounds it. Minimum and maximum temperatures are about 18⁰c and 31.3⁰ c, respectively. However, extremes usually occur in February, when the temperature can exceed 35⁰c. Teso slopes from east to west, thus it receives discharges from the Karamoja highlands and Sebei uplands. This occasionally creates flooding. The sub-region is known for ox-traction with an economy based on subsistence agriculture and livestock rearing. Major crops grown are millet, sorghum, beans, rice, maize and cassava. Livestock reared are pigs, goats, sheep, cattle and poultry such as chicken and turkeys. Fishing is also done in the fresh water of Lake Kyoga.

3.2 Sample selection and sample size

Cluster sampling was used to select 120 households. Out of the eight districts in Teso sub-region, three districts were randomly selected, namely: Soroti, Kumi and Bukedea. Out of each district, one sub county was selected randomly. From the sub county, two parishes were selected also by random sampling. Out of the parishes, two villages were selected by random sampling. Out of the villages selected, ten (10) respondents were selected by random

selection. Systematic random sampling was also conducted among the major weekly markets within the districts. The first 10 respondents were interviewed from every big market day in the district. The total number of respondents from the weekly markets was 30 and the overall sample was 150 respondents.

3.3 Data collection and data types

The survey involved collection of primary data from households who are the prime consumers of sorghum grain. Interviews were administered using a structured questionnaire to consumers. The questionnaire comprised of two sections; the first section included questions on consumers' socio-economic characteristics such as age, income, gender, and household size, and educational level. Data of this kind was necessary because it was conceptualized that these factors influence consumer preference and willingness to pay. The second section contained four choice scenarios and the respondent would be required to choose a variety from each choice scenario based on his/her preference. This kind of data enabled me to evaluate the trade-offs consumers made between attributes and price.

Prior to data collection, the questionnaire was pre-tested on 10 respondents in Malera Sub-county, Bukedea district. The essence was to verify whether the questions were relevant and appropriate; whether the respondents would be in position to evaluate the four choice situations; and to ensure that the enumerators get acclimatized with administering the questionnaire. The pre-testing indicated that the questions were appropriate and that consumers could comfortably handle the four choice tasks.

3.4 Experimental design

The survey used a CE design. A CE started with defining sorghum grain in terms of its attributes and levels taken by these attributes. The most important sorghum attributes and

their levels were identified through focus group discussions (FGDs) with key informants including household sorghum grain consumers specifically the elderly, and also from previous studies on sorghum consumption. An additional monetary attribute, purchase price, was included to capture the marginal WTP for the attributes. Summary of the results from FGDs are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Summary of the results from focus group discussions

Question	Response
How many sizes of sorghum grain do you know? Which are those sizes? Is there a medium size?	There are only two sizes basing on the varieties known. These are small and big.
What is the colour of sorghum grain? Which colour do you prefer for <i>atap</i> ?	There are four colours, namely: red, brown, cream and white. Red is preferred because it does not stick and it has good smell.
What texture of <i>atap</i> do you prefer?	Atap that does not stick is preferred. The one that sticks is not good.
How many tastes of <i>atap</i> do you know? Which one do you prefer?	Three are known but two are common. The common ones are sour and good taste. The rare one is bitter. Good taste is preferred for <i>atap</i> but <i>ajon</i> that is sour is preferred.
Does <i>atap</i> have smell?	There is good smell and one that is not good. One with good smell is preferred.
What is the price of sorghum grain in the market during the bumper harvest?	650 per kilogram
What is the price of sorghum grain in the market during the slack period?	1000 per kilogram
What was the lowest price of sorghum grain ever?	400 per kilogram
What was the highest price of sorghum grain ever?	1650 per kilogram

Following focus group discussions with key informants, the attributes and levels and their analytic coding that were used in a CE design are reported in Table 2.

Table 2: Sorghum grain attributes, their levels and coding

Attribute	Definition	Level and coding
Grain size	The average size of the grain at harvest	0 – Small 1 – Big
Grain colour	The colour of the pericarp at harvest	0 – Red 1 – White 3 – Cream/khaki 4 - Brown
Texture	The texture of sorghum bread while eating	0 – Not elastic/sticky 1- Elastic/extensible
Taste	The taste of sorghum bread and porridge while eating/drinking	0 – Neutral 1 – Good/sweet taste 2 - Sour
Smell	The smell of the product (Atapa or Ajor) made out of the grain	0 – Not good 1 – Good
Price	Hypothetical change in price of sorghum grain per kilogram	0 – 400 1 – 650 2 – 1000 3 - 1650

3.4.1 Construction of choice sets

In a CE design, different experimental procedures can significantly influence the accuracy of the results. Scarpa & Rose (2008) recommended use of an experimental design approach that maximizes an efficiency criterion (such as D – efficiency), or equivalently, minimizes an error criterion such as the D-error. Such an efficient design aims at minimizing standard errors of choice model parameter estimates during the design stage (Rose *et al.*, 2008).

Given the large geographical scope of the study areas and the cost of surveys of this kind, focus was on maximizing the D – optimality through a two-stage design procedure. First, a conventional fractional factorial orthogonal design was used in a preliminary survey of 40 consumers to obtain prior coefficients (Appendix VI). These prior coefficients (henceforth priors) were then used in the second stage to generate Bayesian efficient designs using NGENE 4 software (NGENE used to combine the levels of attributes into a number of alternatives of profiles to be presented to consumers). Bayesian designs allow taking into account uncertainty about the true value of priors used to construct the asymptotic variance-Covariance (AVC) matrix (ChoiceMetrics, 2012). The Bayesian efficient design had a relatively good level of D-optimality (D – efficiency of 85.7%). In addition, the design had a good utility balance (a B- estimate of 82%), which indicates that there was an insignificant likelihood of dominance by any alternative in the choice situations. The final Bayesian design had 24 paired choice profiles (choice profiles attached on the questionnaire in Appendix I) that were randomly blocked into six sets of four choice tasks. Respondents were randomly assigned to one of the six sets. Each choice task consisted of two alternatives (A and B) and a baseline alternative (C) in which all grain attributes were set at the ‘zero level’. The choice experiment was unlabeled (or unbranded) in the sense that the alternative grains had generic titles (A or B) so that they could only be differentiated according to their attribute combinations. In other words, the choice between ‘Grain A’ and ‘Grain B’ could be explained only by their respective attributes (colour, texture, taste, smell and price) but not by their title (A or B). In making their choices, respondents were asked to consider only the attributes presented in the choice tasks and to treat each choice task independently. An example of a choice set presented to respondents is shown in Table 3. Pilot testing of the CE questionnaire was conducted through face – to- face interviews of 12 respondents to refine its

wording and format. The pilot survey showed that respondents could comfortably handle four choice tasks.

Table 3: Showing example of a choice set

Choose your most preferred type of variety from the following three alternatives			
Grain attribute	Alternative A	Alternative B	Alternative C
Colour	Brown	Red	NO CHOICE
Taste	Good	Sour	
Texture	Elastic	Elastic	
Smell	Good	Good	
Size	Big	Small	
Price	400	650	
Which one would you prefer?	1 = Yes 0 = NO	1 = Yes 0 = NO	1 = Yes 0 = NO

3.5 Data processing and analysis

Data obtained were coded and edited to ensure accuracy, validity, uniformity, consistency and completeness. A statistical package, specifically STATA was used to generate descriptive statistics such as the mean, standard deviations and percentages, whereas Nlogit 5 software was used to analyze the discrete choices from the CE. Discrete choice analysis using a Multinomial Conditional Logit (MNCL) model and a Mixed Logit (ML) was used to estimate the extent to which sorghum grain attributes influence preference for sorghum varieties. OLS estimation was undertaken to study the influence of consumer characteristics on the WTP for sorghum grain attributes.

3.6 Analytical methods

Consumers' decisions from a CE are frequently analyzed with the discrete choice modeling framework which assumes that consumers associate each alternative i in a choice set with a utility level and choose the option that provides them with the greatest utility (Michaud *et al.*, 2012). Modeling consumers' choices allows us to estimate how they would trade-off different levels of grain attributes against prices (Loureiro *et al.*, 2001).

3.6.1 Theoretical modeling

The theoretical model arises from consumer theory developed by Lancaster (1966) & Rosen (1974), which postulates that preferences of goods are a function of the attributes possessed by the good rather than by the good per se, expressed as:

$$Y = f(X), \quad (1)$$

where Y is the preference (measured as the choice made from among the three alternatives) and X is a set of product attributes.

The attributes of a good in turn generate utility to an individual. This permits the analysis of consumers' preferences in terms of the utility they perceive to result from various sorghum grain attributes.

Given a set of alternatives (A, B and "opt-out), respondents made a choice of which of the three they would prefer to purchase based on the utility they derive from the consumption of the product. Repeated choices by respondents from sets of alternatives revealed the trade-offs that they were willing to make between attributes. The choice that the respondent made was modeled as a function of the attributes using Random Utility Theory (RUT). Following Lancaster (1966), an individual i is assumed to consider the full set of offered profile

alternatives and to choose the alternative j with the highest utility. This utility is represented in a discrete choice model by a utility expression of the general form,

$$U_{ij} = V(X_{ij}) + \varepsilon_{ij} \quad (2)$$

U_{ij} is the latent unobservable utility level that the i^{th} consumer obtains from choosing the j^{th} grain type.

Equation (2) shows that utility is composed of two parts; systematic/deterministic component (V) that is a function of observable attributes (X_{ij}) and a random component ε_{ij} . Thus, the indirect utility function is:

$$V_{jn} = \alpha + \beta X_{ij} \quad (3)$$

$$U_{ij} = \alpha + \beta X_{ij} + \varepsilon_{ij} \quad (4)$$

Where X_{ij} is a vector of observed variables that includes the product attributes; β s are the utility (or taste) parameters to be estimated, α is a constant – it captures the average effects on utility from attributes not included in the X vector.

3.6.2 Establishing grain attributes preferred by sorghum consumers

Following the theoretical specification (4), the econometric model used to specify utility for a decision-maker i , choosing option j ('grain A' or 'grain B' or 'do not buy') is a function of the characteristics of the alternatives j . The systematic part of the utility function of individual i associated with alternative j is modeled as a linear function:

$$Y_{ij} = \alpha + \beta_1 X_{1i} + \beta_2 X_{2i} + \dots + \beta_j X_{ij} + \varepsilon_{ij} \quad (5)$$

Empirically, the explanatory variables selected for this analysis were specified as;

$$Y_{ij} = \alpha + \beta_1 color_{bij} + \beta_2 color_{wij} + \beta_3 color_{cij} + \beta_4 taste_{ij} + \beta_5 size_{ij} + \beta_6 text_{ij} + \beta_7 smell_{ij} + \beta_8 price_{ij} + \varepsilon_{ij}; \quad (6)$$

Where j denotes 'Grain A', 'Grain B', 'do not buy'. Y_{ij} is the observed choice which is a reflection of the latent unobservable utility for grain alternative j by individual i , β is a vector

of coefficients associated with sorghum grain attributes, other variables are defined in Table 4. The model assumed no interaction effects between the variables. In other words, it was assumed that the effect of the level of each product attributes on respondents' preferences was independent of the level of other product attributes. This assumption is critical to ease complexity in analysis if interactions were considered.

Table 4: Definition of variables and expected signs of coefficients

Variable	Variable definition	Expected sign of the coefficient
colorb	brown colour (1 = Yes, 0 = otherwise)	+
colorW	White colour (1 = Yes, 0 = otherwise)	+
colorC	Cream colour (1 = Yes, 0 = otherwise)	+
taste	Taste of atap (1 = Good, 0 = otherwise)	+
size	Size of sorghm grain (1 = big, 0 = small)	+
text	Texture of atap (1 = Elastic/not sticky, 0 = not elastic/sticky)	+
smell	Smell of atap (1 = Good, 0 = not good)	+
price	Price per kilogram (Ug shs) of sorghum (400, 650,1000,1650)	-

For understanding the influence of different attributes on a dependent variable (choice of variety), a Multinomial Conditional Logit (MNCL) model could be employed for this purpose (McFadden, 2001). Using the 600 choices elicited from 150 respondents, a MNCL model was estimated using Nlogit 5.0 student version. The MNCL however, has limitations. Firstly, MNCL assumes that preferences are homogenous across individuals. In reality, individuals have varying taste patterns for the attributes. Part of this variation in preferences could be attributed to varying consumer characteristics, which are not included in the model. Even after inclusion of demographic variables considerable variation would still remain,

according to findings by Revelt & Train (1998). This suggests that preferences vary considerably more than can be explained by observed consumer characteristics. Ignoring heterogeneous preferences does not only result into biased attribute coefficient estimates (Greene, 1997; Fry & Harris, 1998), but also hinders the proper aggregation of welfare measurements across individuals (Train, 2003).-paper-0091.pdf & (Huhtala, 2000). Consequently, the estimated parameters of the MNCL possess the properties of consistency but not the property of efficiency (Fry & Harris, 1998). However, accounting for this heterogeneity enables estimation of unbiased estimates of individual preferences and enhances the accuracy and reliability of estimates of demand, marginal and total welfare (Greene, 1997).

Secondly, in situations with repeated choices over time, the MNCL assumes that unobserved factors are independent over time for each decision maker. Thirdly, through its assumption of independence from irrelevant alternatives (IIA), the MNCL fails to account for varying levels of substitution between choice alternatives. The IIA property, which states that the relative probabilities of two options being chosen are unaffected by introduction or removal of other alternatives (Greene, 1997), was rejected by the Hausman & McFadden (1984) test. This finding indicates that the ML model, which allows random taste variation, fits the data better than the conditional logit model, which assumes fixed taste parameters. Although point estimates are correct (Table 6), standard errors would be inappropriate if the IIA property does not hold (Greene, 1997; Fry & Harris, 1998).

One of the possible solutions to the homogeneity assumption imposed by the MNCL model would be to interact specific individual variables, such as income or gender with various choice attributes (Adamowicz *et al.*, 1997). In such a scenario, heterogeneity was introduced into the basic model framework. However, this method is limited in practice because it requires prior knowledge regarding which individual and choice variables to interact in order

to distinguish groups with similar preferences (Boxall & Adamowicz, 2002). Secondly, inclusion of interaction variables in a model leads to reduction in statistical efficiency, and increases the complexity of the respondent's task (Hair *et al.*, 1992). Reduction of statistical efficiency is brought about having more parameters to estimate while complexity comes in because more hypothetical products must be rated (Hair *et al.*, 1992). In addition, the IIA property imposed by the MNCL model was rejected at 99% by the Hausman & McFadden test (chi square value of 39.8).

An alternative modeling approach that allows preferences to vary across respondents with equivalent characteristics is Random Parameter Logit (RPL)/Mixed Logit (ML) approach (Train, 1998). In addition, the ML model does not require the IIA property. The RPL model was estimated using Nlogit 5.0 student version. All the parameters, except the price attribute which was assumed to have been drawn from a continuous distribution, were specified to be normally distributed, since a normal distribution allows preferences to range between positive and negative for a given attribute (Train, 1998). A lognormal distribution would restrict the range to being of one sign only.

While estimating the ML model, data for 120 respondents was used instead of the whole sample of 150 respondents. Data for each respondent was entered into 12 rows (three alternatives for each of the four choice sets). A sample of 150 respondents would generate 1800 rows which the Nlogit 5.0 student version would not handle. The sample had to be reduced (randomly) bearing in mind that all six blocks of choice sets had to be equally represented in the remaining sample. Subsequently, a sample of 120 respondents was used to run the ML model. The reduction was randomly done, therefore the remaining sample includes questionnaires from both the households and those sampled from the markets.

3.6.3 Determining the consumers' willingness to pay for sorghum quality attributes

The WTP for a product is computed as the Marginal Rate of Substitution (MRS) between the quantity expressed by the attributes and the price (Louviere et al., 2000). Since preferences are modeled as linear functions of the attributes of the product, the MRS between the two attributes is the ratio between the coefficients. The ratio of an attribute coefficient to the price coefficient represents the implicit price (or WTP) of that attribute, also called the part-worth. From equation (6), following Hanemann (1989);

$$\text{WTP} = -1 * \left(\frac{\beta_k}{\beta_8} \right), \quad k= 1, \dots, 7 \quad (7)$$

Where β_k is the estimated coefficient for an attribute level in the choice set and β_8 is the marginal utility given by the coefficient of the price attribute. Each of these ratios is understood as a price change associated with a unit increase in a given attribute.

Expression (7) generated individual specific willingness to pay values for each attribute. See Appendix V for individual specific WTP estimates.

The overall WTP or compensating surplus (CS) welfare measure, which is the total of WTPs for all the attributes, was obtained from

$$\text{CS} = -1 * \frac{(V_1 - V_0)}{\beta_8} \quad (8)$$

where V_1 represents the value of the indirect utility associated with attributes of a variety under consideration, whereas V_0 is the indirect utility of the baseline variety. V_1 and V_0 are obtained by adding up the estimated coefficients of the levels of traits that make up the profiles. In this study, utility for the baseline variety (V_0) was zero, since all the attributes for this variety were set at zero level.

3.6.4 Determining the effect of consumer characteristics on WTP for sorghum attributes

The econometric model used to analyze the effects of consumer characteristics on WTP for the grain characteristics was specified as;

$$WTP_{ij} = \alpha + \beta' X_i + \varepsilon_{ij}, \quad (9)$$

where WTP_{ij} is the WTP by consumer i for attribute j , β is the parameters to be estimated for the consumer characteristics represented by a vector X .

The empirical model was specified as

$$\begin{aligned} WTP_{ij} = & \alpha + \beta_1 \text{gend}_i + \beta_2 \text{age}_i + \beta_3 \text{educ}_i + \beta_4 \text{ocupfarm}_i + \beta_5 \text{ocuptrain}_i + \beta_6 \text{hhsiz}_i + \\ & \beta_7 \text{loghhinc}_i + \beta_8 \text{impvar}_i + \beta_9 \text{landsz}_i + \beta_{10} \text{amtcsmda}_i + \beta_{11} \text{smkts}_i + \beta_{12} \text{sorglnd}_i + \beta_{13} \text{freqcons}_i \\ & + \beta_{14} \text{regcons}_i + \delta_1 \text{locsor}_i + \delta_2 \text{lockum}_i + \lambda \text{choose}_i + \varepsilon_{ij}; \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

where WTP_{ij} is the willingness to pay for a particular attribute derived from equation (7), $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4, \beta_5, \beta_6, \beta_7, \beta_8, \beta_9, \beta_{10}, \beta_{11}, \beta_{12}, \beta_{13}, \delta_1, \delta_2, \lambda$ are the parameters to be estimated, the other explanatory variables are as defined in Table 5.

Model (10) was estimated by Ordinary Least squares (OLS). This included parameter estimation, diagnostic capabilities (tests) for multicollinearity and heteroscedasticity carried out, and correction measures taken.

Table 5: Showing Variable definitions

Variable	Variable definition
gend	Sex of the respondent (1 = female, 0 = male)(%)
age	Age of the respondent (years)
educ	Number of years spent in school
ocupfarm	Primary occupation of the respondent is farming (%) (1 = Yes, 0 = No)
ocuptrain	Respondent does skilled/professional work (%) (1 = Yes, 0 = No)
hhsz	Family size
landsz	Land size owned by the household (acres)
sorglnd	Land acreage under sorghum production (acres)
hhinc (loghhinc)	Household income (Ug. Shs) (log of household income)
impvar	Whether consumer knew about improved variety (1=Yes, 0= No) (%)
amtcsmda	Amount of sorghum consumed per week (in kilograms)
smkts	Whether the respondent knew about any sorghum market/processors (1 = yes; 0 = No)
freqcons	Household is a frequent consumer of atapa (%) (1 = Yes, 0 = No)
regcons	Household is a regular consumer of atapa (%) (1 = Yes, 0 = No)
lockum	Respondent located in Kumi district (1 = Yes, 0 = No)
locsor	Respondent located in Soroti district (1 = Yes, 0 = No)
choose	Respondent choose either variety A/B or opted-out (1 = Yes, 0 = No)

CHAPTER FOUR: RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter presents and discusses the empirical results based on the data collected from 150 sorghum consumers of Kumi, Soroti and Bukedea districts. Results are summarized as means, percentages, and coefficients. The chapter has four subsections, namely: sample description, knowledge about improved varieties, sorghum markets and consumption behaviour; analysis of attributes preferred by consumers of sorghum; estimation of WTP for each attribute (consumer welfare analysis); and effect of consumer characteristics on the WTP for attributes.

4.1 Sample description

The socioeconomic characteristics influence consumer attitude and behaviour, and hence food choice and consequently willingness to pay. These characteristics are presented in the sub-sections below.

4.1.1 Demographic characteristics

The demographic characteristics like age, gender, education are important in such a study of analysing consumer preferences because they influence consumer tastes and preferences and hence WTP for a given attribute (Campiche et al., 2004). The demographic characteristics are presented in Table 6.

Majority (76.1) of the consumers interviewed were male. Soroti district had the highest proportion of male consumers and the statistically significant (p -value < 0.01) implies that the proportion of men among the three districts was different. Average age of the consumers was 44.3, which is the working age group, and hence likely to consumer what they prefer since they have some disposable income. The F-statistic also revealed that mean age of the consumers in the three districts was statistically significant (p -value < 0.05). The average

number of years spent in school for consumers in all the districts was four years, which is below the number of years required for primary education in the Ugandan curriculum. Average household size was eight in Soroti and seven in the remaining districts. Household size partly influences food choices (Stewart *et al.*, 2004). Most (92.3%) of the consumers were depending on farming as their main occupation. This is consistent with the UBOS findings that over 70% of Ugandans are employed in the Agricultural sector. The proportion of consumers with some professional skill was below 6% in all the districts. Average land size owned by the consumers was 4.9 acres. Although average land size seemed to be bigger in Soroti, the F-statistic did not show a significant difference in land size among the three districts. However, the mean land size was statistically significant (p-value < 0.1) between Soroti and Bukedea district. The proportion of land allocated to sorghum growing was highest in Soroti (1.5 ac) and lowest in Bukedea (0.9 ac). The F-statistic revealed that average acreage of land allocated to sorghum in the three districts was statistically significant (p-value < 0.1). Average monthly income was highest in Soroti (Ugshs. 485,960 – equivalent to \$ 194) and lowest in Kumi district (Ugshs. 364,116 - \$146)). This is more than \$1 per day (the poverty line), implying high purchasing power. The average income for consumers among the three districts was statistically significant (p-value < 0.01).

Table 6: Demographic characteristics of the respondents

Variable	Soroti Mean (SD)	Kumi Mean (SD)	Bukedea Mean (SD)	Overall Mean (SD)	chi- F square
Gender(%)	80.8	71.1	76.7	76.1	15.49***
Age (years)	42.9 (14.2)	44.7 (13.0)	45.1 (16.3)	44.3 (14.5)	3.64**
Education (years)	4.3 (3.3)	3.9 (2.9)	4.1 (2.6)	4.1 (3.0)	1.89
Household size	8 (3)	7.0 (3)	7 (3)	7 (3)	14.97***
Farmer occupation(%)	97.9	90.4	88.4	92.3	2.59
Professional (%)	2.1	5.8	0	3.5	2.98
Land size (ac)	5.9 (4.6)	4.9 (4.9)	3.8 (4.1)	4.9 (4.7)	2.16
Land under sorghum	1.5 (1.4)	1.4 (1.6)	0.9 (0.7)	1.3 (1.3)	2.60*
Consumer income (ugx)	485960 (370552)	364116 (266190)	492994 (370688)	443471 (3413449)	27.49***

4.1.2 Consumers' knowledge about improved varieties, sorghum markets and source of grain

Majority of the consumers (76 %) did not know about improved varieties of sorghum (Table 7). Much as the number of consumers who knew about improved varieties seemed to be biggest in Kumi (30.9 %) compared to other districts (20 %), the chi-square value showed that proportion of consumer who knew about improved varieties was not significantly different among the three districts. From the overall sample, 24% knew about improved varieties and had actually ever planted them. A study conducted by 0002x.main revealed that consumer's knowledge on organic was statistically significant on both the probability to buy food products and the probability of being a regular consumer. Most of the respondents (77%) reported that they did not know about sorghum markets (besides the local village markets) and sorghum processors (higher level brewers and millers). The major processing activity done by majority of the respondents was milling and done locally. There was some processing done by Nile Breweries but this processor needed a specific variety of sorghum

which was grown by few. Most of the sorghum consumed at home was obtained from the market (75% of the households) while 55% consume from own production, of which 24% consume purely from own production. The highest percentage of consumers who obtain sorghum from the market is a clear indication that consumption is higher than production. The low production` is further indicated by the smallest proportion of land allocated to sorghum production yet it is frequently consumed. The proportion of land area allocated to sorghum production was less than 30% of total land acreage owned by a household.

Table 7: Consumers' knowledge about improved varieties, sorghum markets and grain source

Characteristic	Soroti	Kumi	Bukedea	Pooled Sample	chi-square
Knowledge about improved varieties					
Yes	20	30.9	20	24	3.22
No	80	69.1	80	76	
Knowledge about sorghum markets or processors					
Yes	24	20	26.7	23.3	1.56
No	76	80	73.3	76.7	
Source of grain for consumption					
Market	53.3	36.2	44.2	44.4	
Own production	11.1	31.9	30.2	24.4	7.99*
Both	35.6	31.9	25.6	31.1	

4.1.3 Sorghum products preferred for consumption and frequency of consumption

Sorghum is consumed in many forms. The major forms of consumption were porridge, local brew (*ajon*) and sorghum bread (*atapa*) (Table 8). Since most respondents reported that they do not take breakfast, consumption in form of porridge was not considered in this study. This study only focused on *atap* and *ajon* as the major forms of consumption. The study revealed that most of the consumption (about 89 %) of sorghum was in form of *atap* and 2 % consume sorghum in form of local brew. Consumers who consumed both sorghum products (*atapa* and local brew) were 8.7% of the total population. There was no respondent who reported consuming sorghum in the form of brew in Kumi district. The fact that over 90 % of the respondents reported being consumers of *atapa*, this study was based on *atapa*. The attributes

that this study sought to elicit were those that were preferred by the consumers of *atapa*. Over 90 % of the respondents consume sorghum frequently (4 – 7 times a week). Indeed sorghum is a major food crop in all the districts under study. The number of frequent consumers was greatest in Kumi district where 98% were frequent consumers. However, consumption per week was highest in Soroti district (about 6 kg per week). Frequency of consumption influences WTP for sorghum. For instance, in a study conducted to examine demand relationships and WTP for organic, no-antibiotics used and conventional milk, being a frequent milk or organic buyer led to higher WTP (Bernard and Bernard, 2009). The highest weekly consumption was high in Soroti partly due to the fact that households in Soroti were big (eight members) compared to those of other districts whose households had less members (Table 6). Average weekly consumption of sorghum was also significantly different (p-value < 0.01) among the three districts.

Table 8: Sorghum product preferred and frequency of consumption

Characteristic	Soroti	Kumi	Bukedea	Pooled Sample	Chi-square	F
Form of sorghum consumption (5%)						
Atapa	89.4	84.6	93.0	89.3		
Local brew (Ajono)	2	0	4.4	2.0	7.02	
Atapa and Brew	8	14.5	2.2	8.7		
Sorghum product preferred for consumption (%)						
Atapa	97.9	100	95.3	98	2.46	
Ajono	2	0	4.4	2		
Frequency of sorghum consumption a week (%)						
Frequently (4–7 times)	91.3	98.1	95.1	94.6		
Regularly (2–3 times)	6.1	1.8	4.7	4.1	2.98	
Occasionally (once)	2.2	0	2.4	1.4		
Weekly consumption (kg)	5.7	3.6	3.2	4.6	5.81***	

4.2 Sorghum grain attributes preferred by consumers

In all models run for different districts and the overall sample, the F-statistics were statistically significant at 1 percent level implying that the attributes jointly affected consumers' preference for sorghum (Table 9). The effect of attributes on consumer preference in the pooled sample was similar to the effect exhibited in the individual districts. In other words, all attributes (except) price had a positive effect on consumers' preference. This implies that increments on any of the attributes increase the utility level, while the negative price coefficient suggests that increase in the price reduces the associated utility level of the consumer. This is consistent with the prior signs presented in chapter 3 (Table 4).

ML results of the pooled sample indicate that all coefficients had a positive and statistically significant effect on consumers' preference (Table 8). These results are consistent with Kayode *et al* (2005); Cardello, 1994; Subramanian & Jambunathan (1992) findings from previous studies that the quality criteria used in choosing food products relate to texture, taste, colour and smell. All colour attributes had a positive (but varying) effect and this effect is consistent with the findings of Mafuru (2007) and Laswai et al., (2003) that colour was the most important criteria for acceptability of sorghum pastes and beverages. Brown colour had a positive and statistically significant effect on consumers' preference in Soroti district, but had no significant effect in other districts. Consumers reported that their affinity for the brown colour was due to the fact that it makes *atapa* that is attractive to the eyes of the consumer. White colour had a positive and statistically significant effect in all districts. The preference for white colour is consistent with results obtained by Hugo & Kimenju (2008), that consumers had a strong preference for white maize. Rooney & Murty (1982a) also found out that there was a universal preference for white-coloured sorghum products. Further, white grains are better for food quality because they mill without any possibility of colour contaminating the flour during decortications (Aboubacar *et al.*, 1999). However, the finding that white colour is most preferred of all the colours is inconsistent with what is on the ground. In reality, *atapa* consumers prefer *atapa* made out of either brown or red sorghum. This inconsistency could be due to the elastic texture (coefficient = 0.83) and good smell (coefficient= 1.09) that are valued higher than white colour (Table 9). It is likely that a consumer substitutes these two attributes for colour. In other words, preference for colour comes after good smell and elastic texture. The effect of cream colour was also found to be positive and highly significant in all (except Bukedea) districts. Cream colour was also preferred but not as much as white and brown. This is consistent with findings of Rooney & Murty (1982a), that there is a universal preference for white- and cream-coloured sorghum

products. The reasons for preference for white colour are the same reasons that explain preference for cream colour.

Good taste also had a positive and significant effect on consumers' preference in Soroti and Bukedea districts but the attribute had no significant effect in Kumi district. This implies that if a variety had a good taste, it would be easily acceptable for consumption. Dinis *et al.*, (2011) also found out that consumers preferred apples with a better taste. Furthermore, Mafuru *et al.*, (2007) found out that taste was the most important criteria used by consumers to evaluate the quality of sorghum 'ugali'. Further, the results indicate that colour attributes had a greater effect than taste, but taste is more paramount. Colour is likely to matter especially to first time purchasers of sorghum, but repeated purchases seem likely to be more affected by taste (Melton *et al.*, 1996).

Consumers in Soroti and Bukedea expressed preference for 'atapa' that is elastic, as shown by the positive and significant coefficients for texture attribute. They reported that 'atapa' which is elastic/extensible does not stick on fingers while eating. In line with the findings of Rooney *et al.*, (1986), texture has been described as being one of the most important characteristics affecting sorghum food quality.

Grain size also had a positive and statistically significant effect on consumer preference. According to the interview with the informant, the bigger the grain, the more it would be preferred because it yields more flour after milling. Grain size was also found to be quite important for food usage in the study conducted by Wills *et al.*, (1992).

Smell attribute had a positive and highly significant effect on consumers' preference in all districts. On the basis of the pooled sample, the smell attribute had the largest coefficient, implying that it affects WTP most. However, a study conducted by Daillant-Spinnler *et al.*,

1995) found out that texture and taste were more important for consumers than aroma of apples.

The price attribute had a negative and statistically significant effect in all the districts. The negative price coefficient implies that, on average, the higher the price, the less likely it would be to choose a given variety. This is consistent with the findings of the study conducted by Thompson & Kidwell (1998), that consumers would be willing to buy more of organic produce at lower than higher prices. However, Gil & Sanchez (1997) found out that price is not relevant to explain consumer preferences.

ML output also displays standard deviations of the parameter estimates (Table 9). These indicate the amount of spread that exists around the sample population. The high and statistically significant standard deviations in the pooled sample analysis reveal that preferences indeed varied in the population for all (except texture) the attributes. This implies that the attribute coefficients are not fixed but significantly vary across individuals. For the texture attribute, consumers had homogenous preferences for the attribute. All the colour attributes had statistically significant standard deviations in Soroti and Kumi districts, implying that preferences for colour attribute varied across consumers in these districts.

Together with the mean coefficient (Table 9), the standard deviation of the distribution of the random parameter permitted computation of proportion of consumers who had negative coefficients and those who had positive ones (Train, 1998, 2000). This was possible since the normal distribution assumed by the random parameters allowed coefficients of both signs to be generated. Thus, for brown colour attribute, the ML showed that 24% of the respondents had negative coefficients for this attribute, while 76% had positive coefficients (analysis based on pooled data). The percentage was obtained from the standard normal distribution curve using the z – value = -0.7 obtained from $(0 - \mu)/SD$, where $\mu = 0.7$ and $SD = 1.00$.

Respondents who had positive coefficients for white, cream and big grain size attributes were 79%, 74% and 98% respectively. Similarly, 72% and 67% of the respondents had positive coefficients for the good taste and good smell attributes respectively. The fact that above 65% of the respondents had positive coefficients for the attributes explains why the coefficients were positive. Big grain size had the highest proportion of consumers with a positive coefficient, implying that this attribute positively influenced preference of many consumers compared to other attributes. Good smell had the smallest proportion of consumers with a positive coefficient for the attribute, implying that it positively influenced the least number of consumers.

Table 9: Mixed Logit model estimates of grain attributes preferred by sorghum consumers

Attribute	Soroti (n=50)	Kumi (n=55)	Bukedea (n=45)	Pooled sample (n=120)
ColorB	0.89(2.16)**	1.44(0.78)	0.93(1.57)	0.70(2.45)**
ColorW	1.57(3.22)***	4.78(2.25)**	1.77(2.38)**	0.81(2.75)***
ColorC	1.18(2.88)***	3.88(2.26)**	0.43(0.86)	0.63(2.38) **
Taste	1.82(3.90)***	0.89(0.61)	1.49(1.9)*	0.53(1.76)*
Text	0.94(2.91)***	1.58(1.24)	1.34(2.22)**	0.83(3.44)***
Smell	1.07(2.49)**	4.66(3.10)***	2.27(2.86)***	1.09(4.49) ***
Size	0.92(2.87)***	3.07(2.45)**	0.68(1.23)	0.42(1.98) **
Price	-0.0005(-1.74)*	-0.0015(-1.74)*	-0.0022(-3.57)***	-0.0076(-4.09)***
Standard deviations of parameter distributions				
sdColorB	1.01(1.98)**	8.97(1.98)**	1.15(1.54)	1.00(3.34)***
sdColorW	1.01(1.98)**	8.97(1.98)**	1.15(1.54)	1.0(3.34)***
sdColorC	1.01(1.98)**	8.97(1.98)**	1.15(1.54)	1.00(3.34)***
sdTaste	1.28(2.61)***	15.8(3.24)***	3.87(2.60)***	1.91(5.14)***
sdTexture	0.09(0.08)	5.14(2.64)***	1.54(1.69)*	0.40(0.81)
sdSmell	1.2(2.30)**	10.1(3.33)***	2.4(2.34)**	0.98(3.09)***
sdSize	0.69(1.01)	7.26(2.33)**	0.9(1.28)	0.97(2.77)***
Log-likelihood	-190.33	-191.81	-151.28	-467.2
Adjusted R ²	0.105	0.18	0.206	0.102
Chisqrd [Pr(C>c)]	8.99(0.34)	14.7(0.065)	20.9(0.0074)	39.8(0.0000)

*Statistical significance levels: ***1%; **5%; *10%. Corresponding t-ratios are shown in parentheses.*

4.3 Consumer welfare analysis

4.3.1 Consumers WTP for various quality attributes of sorghum

The marginal WTP (implicit price) for a discrete change in an attribute provided a measure of the relative importance that a consumer attaches to attributes that constitute the hypothetical grain varieties. The coefficient for price variable being significant (Table 9) permitted the computation of trade-offs between each attribute and money. The implicit prices/ marginal WTP values for each of the sorghum attributes were estimated using the Wald procedure (Delta method) in LIMDEP 10.0/NLOGIT 5.0.

WTP estimates for each attribute are presented in Table 10, and were all positive. Pooled sample results indicate that a consumer would be willing to pay between Ugshs 86 and Ugshs 2048 per kilogram for white colour attribute; Ugshs 77 to Ugshs 1581 for cream colour attribute and Ugshs 416 to Ug shs 1780 for elastic texture attribute. Big grain attribute had the smallest coefficient (as per ML results) of all the attributes, implying that it had the least effect on consumers' preference. No wonder, WTP for big grain size was not statistically significant. Much as big grain size had a positive and statically significant coefficient, it was not worth paying for. This outcome was consistent with the findings of Ricardo & Willis (2010) in a study to investigate WTP for renewable energy technologies in the UK, and found that much as households valued renewable energy, the value was not significantly large to justify payment for renewable energy.

The amount that consumers would be willing to pay for a given attribute depended upon the magnitude of the effect of that attribute on the Consumers' preference. In other words, the higher the attribute coefficient (Table 9), the higher the amount that consumers would be willing to pay for the attribute. Good smell had the largest coefficient followed by elastic texture and their price premiums followed suit. Therefore, consumers valued good smell

highest followed by elastic texture of 'atapa'. Good smell attribute was valued highest in Soroti and Kumi districts. This finding is consistent with one obtained by Dinis *et al.*, (2011), that consumers were willing to pay a higher price for apples with a better smell. For most of the attributes, consumers in Soroti would pay the highest price premium, while those in Bukedea would pay the least.

The results also imply that WTP of brown, white and cream colours was normally distributed with mean Ug shs 915, 1067 and 829, respectively; and the standard deviation of WTP for the colour attributes was Ug shs 132 (1.00/0.0076). Similarly, WTP of smell and taste attributes was normally distributed with means Ug shs 1433 and 703, respectively. The standard deviation of WTP for smell and taste attributes was Ug shs 129 (0.98/0.0076) and 251 (1.91/0.0076), respectively. This large standard deviation represents an important variation in WTP in the population. With a fixed price coefficient, WTP follows the distribution of the random parameter.

Table 10: Marginal WTP estimates for the sorghum quality attributes (Ug shs)

Attribute	Soroti (n=50)	Kumi (n=55)	Bukedea (n=45)	Pooled sample (n=120)
colorB	1792(-1149 – 4733)	943(-1469 - 3354)	425(-143 – 994)	915(-24 – 1855) ^c
ColorW	3160(-908 - 7228)	3134(401 - 5867) ^b	806(-129 - 1483) ^b	1067(86 – 2048) ^b
colorC	2371(-532 - 5274)	2542(580 - 4504) ^b	196(-260 - 651)	829(77 - 1581) ^b
Taste	3666(-281 - 7613) ^c	581(-1340 - 2502)	681(-61 - 1422) ^c	703(-81 - 1487) ^c
Texture	1889(-236 - 4013) ^c	1036(-591 - 2663)	611(165 - 1058) ^a	1098(416 - 1780) ^a
Size	1859(-738 - 4456)	2015(317 - 3713) ^b	313(-170 - 796)	547(-113 - 1207)
Smell	2146(-237 - 4530) ^c	3054(1207 - 4901) ^a	1038(478 - 1599) ^a	1433(651 – 2214) ^a

95% Confidence intervals are in parentheses; superscripts a,b,c indicate significances at 1%, 5%, 10% respectively.

4.3.2 Total WTP for grain varieties

The overall WTP or compensating surplus (CS) welfare measure was obtained for different variety scenarios associated with multiple changes in attribute levels. CS is the total WTP for a given variety and is obtained by adding the WTP estimates for the individual attribute. To illustrate how consumers in different districts might respond to varieties with different combinations of attributes, CS estimates were derived for five possible varietal scenarios (Table 11). For the purpose of understanding the results in Table 10, refer to the coding sheet for the attributes in Table 2. The attributes with “Ø” symbol indicate attribute level with code “1” and where this symbol is not indicated, it is an attribute level with code “0”. For example, variety 3 is: “Cream” colour (code 1), “bitter” taste (code 0), “not elastic” texture (code 0), ‘not good’ smell (code 0) and “big” grain size (code 1).

The positive CS estimates suggest that generally consumers prefer a change from the baseline variety. Varieties with such attributes would be accepted by consumers. WTP for variety 2 was greater in Kumi than in Bukedea. This could be due the fact that Kumi district has more frequent consumers (98.1%) than Bukedea (95.1%) (Table 8). In addition, average weekly consumption was higher in Kumi (3.6kg) than in Bukedea (3.2kg). These two factors coupled together lead to higher sorghum demand in Kumi, and hence greater WTP. Generally, the total WTP for the varieties was greatest in Soroti district and least in Bukedea district.

Table 11: Attribute levels and compensating surplus for hypothetical sorghum grain varieties (in Ugshs)

Variety	Attribute							Compensating surplus per district			
	Colb	Colw	Colc	Taste	Text	Smell	Size	Soroti	Kumi	Bukedea	Pooled sample
1			∅					2371(1481)	2542(1001) ^b	196(232)	829(384) ^b
2	∅						∅	3651(2648)	2958(1517) ^c	738(410) ^c	1462(687) ^b
3			∅				∅	4230(2630)	4557(1519) ^a	509(345)	1376(561) ^b
4		∅		∅		∅		8972(5009) ^c	4396(2454) ^c	2525(716) ^a	3202(1031) ^a
5				∅	∅		∅	7413(4167) ^c	1730(1454)	1605(545) ^a	2348(776) ^a

Notes: Standard errors are in parentheses. ∅ indicates attribute level with code '1', otherwise code '0'. superscripts a,b,c indicate significances at 1%, 5%, 10% respectively.

Basing on the original coding in Table 2, the actual attribute levels that constituted the five hypothetical varieties in Table 10 are presented in Table 12. Each row is a variety (hypothetical) with different attribute levels. For example, variety 5 is a grain variety with red colour, sweet taste, big grain size, and would give *atap* with elastic texture and ‘not good’ smell. The total WTP for that variety with those attributes would be Ugshs. 2348 per kilogram.

Among the five hypothetical varieties, 4 and 5 turned out with the largest total willingness to pay value. Total WTP for variety 4 was highest due to the presence of good smell that was strongly preferred (Table 10). Variety 5 turned out second largest due to the presence of elastic texture, also strongly preferred. This implies that the presence of elastic texture or good smell suppresses colour. This is also consistent with the key informants’ responses (Table 1) who reported that they prefer red/brown sorghum because of its texture, smell and taste.

Note that variety 4 with a white colour is valued higher than variety 5 with red colour. Consider change of colour of variety 4 from white to brown (Variety 4a) or to cream (variety 4b). Total willingness to pay for variety 4a and 4b would be 3051 and 2965, respectively, which is still high. Therefore, provided a variety has good smell and sweet taste, it will be preferred regardless of its colour.

Table 12: Attribute combinations for the hypothetical varieties

Attribute Variety	Colour	Taste	Texture	Smell	Grain size	CS (based on pooled data)
1	Red	Bitter	Not elastic	Not good	Small	829
2	Brown	Bitter	Not elastic	Not good	Big	1462
3	Cream	bitter	Not elastic	Not good	Big	1376
4	White	Sweet	Not elastic	Good	Small	3202
<i>4a</i>	<i>Brown</i>	<i>Sweet</i>	<i>Not elastic</i>	<i>Good</i>	<i>Small</i>	<i>3051</i>
<i>4b</i>	<i>Cream</i>	<i>Sweet</i>	<i>Not elastic</i>	<i>Good</i>	<i>Small</i>	<i>2965</i>
5	Red	Sweet	Elastic	Not good	Big	2348

4.4 The effect of consumer characteristics on the WTP for the grain attributes

OLS regression models using pooled sample data were run for each of the attributes to determine the effect of consumer characteristics on the WTP for the attribute (Table 13). Standardized coefficients are indicated in parentheses to facilitate comparison of the relative strengths of the predictor variables. The F-statistics for all the models were statistically significant implying that consumer characteristics jointly affected WTP. Regression model for size attribute was not considered because its WTP was found to be statistically insignificant during estimation of WTP for grain size.

Table 13: OLS estimates for effects of consumer characteristics on the WTP for grain attributes

Variable	WcolB	WcolW	WcolC	Wtaste	Wtext	Wsmell
Constant	2685.2 ^a	1064.4 ^a	1043.6 ^a	-5008.7 ^a	744.4 ^a	1349.9 ^a
Lockum	-89.2(-0.08) ^b	-65.5(-0.06) ^b	90.1(0.09) ^a	317.6(0.09) ^a	-20.7(-0.07) ^b	-
locsor	-124.9(-0.11) ^a	-	60.8(0.06) ^c	931.5(0.25) ^a	26.8(0.08) ^b	73.4(0.05) ^c
gend	-98.8(-0.08) ^a	-	-	1008.0(0.25) ^a	-	130.2(0.08) ^a
age	-	-4.1(-0.11) ^a	-3.3(-0.1) ^a	28.5(0.24) ^a	1.28(0.12) ^a	-1.52(-0.03)
educ	51.4(0.28) ^a	-9.3(-0.05) ^c	7.6(0.05)	45.9(0.08) ^c	-7.2(-0.14) ^a	-20.6(-0.09) ^a
ocupfarm	110.8(0.06) ^c	140.7(0.08) ^b	-	-	-134.2(-0.25) ^a	-778.1(-0.34) ^a
ocuptrain	456.8(0.17) ^a	388.1(0.15) ^a	-238.0(-0.10) ^a	-	-91.1(-0.12) ^a	-1199.4(-0.36) ^a
loghinc	-381.9(-0.29) ^a	133.9(0.11) ^a	-	608.7(0.15) ^a	86.6(0.23) ^a	151.8(0.09) ^a
impvar	227.9(0.18) ^a	-	-	-	-53.4(-0.15) ^a	-77.8(-0.05) ^b
landsz	13.2(0.15) ^a	11.7(0.14) ^a	7.04(0.1) ^c	22.4(0.08) ^c	-4.6(-0.18) ^a	-22.3(-0.20) ^a
smkts	-95.1(-0.07) ^b	54.0(0.04)	-54.9(-0.05) ^c	-419.2(-0.10) ^a	39.3(0.11) ^a	383.4(0.24) ^a
amtcsmda	33.1(0.26) ^a	-38.0(-0.32) ^a	-13.3(-0.12) ^a	16.1(0.04)	-3.7(-0.11) ^a	-7.25(-0.05) ^c
sorglnd	-88.7(-0.25) ^a	-95.2(-0.28) ^a	-28.4(-0.09) ^c	-56.1(-0.05)	8.7(0.09) ^c	76.9(0.18) ^a
hhsz	-13.6(-0.08) ^b	14.8(0.10) ^a	24.0(0.17) ^a	-	-2.01(-0.05)	-
freqcons	163.3(0.05)	-511.2(-0.18) ^a	-277.6(-0.11) ^a	-322.8(-0.03)	-	-
regcons	462.9(0.11) ^a	-413.4(-0.10) ^a	-319.8(-0.09) ^b	-	-	-
Adj. R ²	0.1770	0.139	0.051	0.1636	0.1444	0.1770

Standardized coefficients (in parentheses) are indicated in parenthesis for the purpose of comparing the relative strength of the various predictors. a = ***, b = **, c = *

Location of the consumer was found to have a statistically significant effect on the WTP for all sorghum attributes. In Soroti district, consumers were less willing to pay for brown colour. This is inconsistent with the reality. If evaluated alone, brown sorghum is preferred, but because evaluation involved all attributes at once, brown colour was suppressed. In the districts, consumers were more willing to pay for good taste. On the other hand, a consumer who was located in Kumi district was less likely to pay white colour. The dislike for white colour could be due to two reasons. First, consumers dislike improved varieties (white perceived as improved because it has just been introduced) because they cannot be stored long so that they can ensure household food security as insects/pests attack them easily. Secondly, improved varieties, having big grain size, have a big proportion of floury endosperm and these results into higher dehulling losses (Laswai *et al.*, 2003). Similarly, a consumer's location in Soroti (*locsor*) also had a positive influence on WTP for good taste, elastic texture and good smell. The positive effect of Soroti location was greatest on the WTP for sweet/good taste. This finding is consistent with the ML results where this attribute coefficient was greatest. Although location was found to have significant effect on the WTP, Huang (1996) found out that location had no significant impact of accepting Organic Food products.

Gender of the consumer was also found to have a statistically significant a positive effect on the WTP for good taste and good smell (Table 13). This finding could be attributed to the fact that most (80%) of the respondents were women and they are the ones who prepare *atap* for food. The positive effect is consistent with the studies conducted by Carlos *et al.*, (2005) and Ariyawardana *et al.*, (2009), who found out that women were willing to pay a premium for organic food. On the other hand, women had a lower WTP for yellow maize (Hugo & Kimenju, 2008).

Age of the consumer was found to have a statistically significant negative influence on the WTP for white colour and cream colour (Table 13). They instead opt for the varieties that make good 'atapa'. Kayode *et al.*, (2005) found out that older people dislike white sorghum bread because it is perceived to cause diarrhoea. The effect of age on WTP for white and cream colour is contrary to expectation. From the nutritional point of view, white or cream sorghum should be preferred because it has no tannin that hinders nutrition. Tannins precipitate proteins thereby reducing their availability to the body (Hahn *et al.*, 1984). Therefore, the elderly, who are more concerned about nutritional benefits, would be expected to be willing to pay for cream or white sorghum. Nevertheless, the negative effect of age is also consistent with the results obtained by Onyango *et al.*, (2006) that younger consumers are more likely to buy organic foods. In contrast, Millock *et al.*, (2004) found out that age of the consumer significantly increases the probability of being a heavy consumer of organic food. Age also had a statistically significant and positive effect on the WTP for sweet/good taste and elastic texture. For the elderly, the immediate need is food. That's why they are willing to pay for sweet/good taste and elastic texture because these are attributes of good 'atap'.

The study revealed that education level of the consumer had a statistically significant and positive effect on the WTP for brown colour. Consumers who are educated are likely to adopt technologies faster than those who are not. The educated can easily access information about new technologies and are in most cases aware of what is embedded in the new technologies. That's why improved light brown varieties like 'Seso 3' would be easily purchased by consumers who are educated. The positive effect of education is consistent with the findings obtained by Loureiro & Hine, (2001) that the likelihood to purchase organic products and pay a premium increased with increase in education level. Education level had a negative effect on the WTP for white colour. This implies that as the education level of the consumer

increases, they become less likely to buy sorghum with white colour. This is in agreement with the findings obtained by Lockie *et al.*, (2004) that more educated people are less likely to buy organic food. Similarly, Misra *et al.*, (1991) found out that consumers with a college education were less likely to pay more for certified-FPR produce.

Household income was found to have a statistically significant and positive effect on sweet/good taste, elastic texture and good smell. The greatest positive effect of household income was on the WTP for elastic texture followed by sweet/good taste. As ones income increases, they can afford to buy sorghum with enhanced attributes like good taste, elastic texture and good smell which make good 'atap'. The positive effect of household income was also obtained from a study conducted by SteeKamp (1996) that the choice of a product depends on income of the consumer.

Household size had a positive effect on the WTP for white and cream colours. White and cream sorghum grains are perceived to have bigger size than brown grain. Consumers prefer sorghum with big grains because it gives more flour after milling. Therefore households with many members would be willing to buy white and cream due to its big grain size. In addition, it is likely that big households have many children, and would therefore be concerned about the nutritional value of their food. Brown sorghum is believed to have tannin which hinders protein availability in the body, hence being disliked. The negative effect of household size was also obtained by Loureiro *et al.*, (2001) that shoppers with large families were less likely to purchase organic apples.

Knowledge about improved varieties had a negative influence on the WTP for elastic texture and good smell (Table 13). This is contrary to the expectation. It would be expected that a consumer who knows improved varieties should be in position to access those with elastic texture and good smell. This finding is also inconsistent with the results obtained by Von

Alvesteben (1997) and Yiridoe *et al.*, (2005) that product knowledge is an important factor that positively influences purchase decision for food products. Gracia & Tiziana (2007) also found out that the higher the knowledge about organic foods, the more likely it is that they buy organic food products. A study conducted by Akankwasa (2010) also revealed that consumers' awareness was positively associated with consumer acceptability and WTP for desert bananas.

It was also found out that amount of sorghum consumed per week had a positive effect on the WTP good taste. Consumers whose weekly consumption is high would also be willing to pay for sorghum with a good taste.

CHAPTER FIVE: CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Conclusions

There had not been any initiative to elicit the important sorghum grain attributes that consumers base on while selecting sorghum for consumption. Most of the studies have been done on producer preferences for sorghum but few elucidate consumer attributes. The major grain attributes that consumers of sorghum prefer were elicited and the WTP for the attributes. These attributes were also consolidated into hypothetical varieties in order to evaluate them for consumer acceptability. This is particularly important as far as marketability of sorghum is concerned.

Literature indicates that preferences vary among consumers due to varying consumer characteristics. The study, thus, took into account heterogeneity of consumers while eliciting important quality attributes using the ML model.

It was revealed that all attributes jointly influenced consumers' preference and consumers had heterogeneous preferences. Good smell and extensible/elastic texture came out as strongly preferred attributes and appeared to suppress colour. White colour was more preferred than other colours, which is inconsistent with what is preferred in reality. According to the key informants, the red and brown sorghum are preferred because of their elastic texture and good smell. Thus colour could have been suppressed by texture and smell in the estimation, especially since the evaluation was conducted on the combined attributes.

The willingness to pay estimates were positive for all attributes, implying that consumers would want to change from the current varieties. The higher the attribute coefficient, the higher the willingness to pay estimate for the attribute. Therefore, the willingness to pay estimates portray how important an attribute is to the consumer. Worth noting however, was

that much as big grain size had a statistically significant effect, its willingness to pay was not significant. This implies that its significance does not warrant payment.

Consumer characteristics were also found to have significant effects on the WTP for different attributes. A consumer who was located in Kumi was more likely to pay for cream colour and good taste, but less likely to pay for brown and white colours. Female consumers were more willing to pay for good taste. The elderly were more willing to pay for good taste and elastic texture. On the other hand, the elderly were less willing to pay for white and cream colours. A consumer with a higher level of education was more willing to pay for brown and cream colour. Income of the consumer positively influences willingness to pay for white colour, good taste and extensible/elastic texture but negatively influences WTP for brown colour. Households with many members were more willing to pay for white and cream colour but less likely to pay for brown colour and elastic texture.

From willingness to pay results, good smell and elastic texture came out strongly as preferred attributes. According to the key informants, preference for red and brown sorghum was due to their good smell and elastic texture of *atap*. Hence colour could be suppressed by these attributes and only expressed through the two attributes.

From the study, that there was considerable preference heterogeneity within the sorghum consumers, which should be taken into consideration when designing provision of new varieties. The idea of heterogeneity is important for the grain industry to segment the market and offer suitable products to respective consumer segments.

5.2 Recommendations

Good smell and elastic texture were strongly preferred. Therefore, breeders should take into consideration smell and texture of sorghum grain when developing new sorghum varieties.

There was preference heterogeneity among sorghum consumers. Heterogeneity was partly due gender, income of the consumer, and location of the consumer. Knowledge of heterogeneity is important to enable breeders develop sorghum varieties for specific consumer segments.

Attributes were valued highest in Soroti, therefore, those interested in business (profits) should target this market.

5.3 Future research

This study focused on consumption at the household level. Further research is needed to elicit the grain attributes preferred by other consumers (like the higher level breweries, grain millers, and animal feed manufacturers) in the sorghum grain marketing chain. Secondly, further research is needed to evaluate sorghum colours independently from other attributes to determine which colour dominates. Thirdly, the research revealed that consumers had heterogeneous preferences for sorghum attributes but never segmented the consumers. Future research should segment consumers according to their preferences.

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Codes: Gender (0. Male 1. Female)

- Occupation:
- 0. Student
 - 1. Administrative/Managerial Retired/Pensioner
 - 2. Farmer
 - 3. Skilled/Technically Trained
 - 4. Business
 - 5. Laborer/Domestic
 - 6.
 - 7. Housewife
 - 8. Unemployed
 - 9. Other.....

Production of sorghum

1. Have you grown any improved variety of sorghum?
0. NO . 1. Yes

2. If yes, name the varieties you have grown?
.....
.....

3. For how long (years) have you grown the variety?

Variety	Years grown
Local varieties	

4. What is the household total land size?
.....acres

5. What is the average land size allocated to sorghum production?
.....acres

6. Do you know any markets or processors for sorghum?
0. No 1. Yes

7. If yes, name them
.....

Consumption of sorghum

8. In what form is sorghum consumed? (bread, beer, etc)
.....
.....

(More than one answer allowed)

Sorghum product	Variety used	Reason why variety is liked
Bread		
Beer		

19. Describe extent of preference for the grain attribute used to make the food product

Food item	Texture/viscoelasticity	Taste	Colour	Size	Smell	Grain hardness
Bread						
Beer						

(coding: 1 = very important; 2 = important; 3 = Not important)

20. If attribute in (-19-) is important, characterize the quality attributes of food item(s).

Food item	Texture/viscoelasticity (elastic, non-elastic)	Taste (bitter, egegeti)	Colour (red, blown, white, cream)	Size (big, small)	Smell (bad, good)	Grain hardness (hard, soft)
Bread						
Beer						

Willingness to pay for the grain and sorghum food products

21. How likely would you be interested in purchasing the food item (**bread**) with characteristics shown on the card? (present a card at a time to the respondent and let him/her choose the best option)

22. How likely would you be interested in purchasing the food item (**beer**) with characteristics shown on the card? (present a card at a time to the respondent and let him/her choose the best option)

23. Which new products made out of sorghum grain would you like to find in the market?

THE CHOICE SETS

Block 1

Scenario 1

	Alternative 1	Alternative 2	Alternative 3
colour	Brown	White	Opt out
taste	Egegeti	Sweet	
texture	Not elastic	Elastic	
smell	Not good	Not good	
size	Big	Small	
price	1,650	400	
Choice question: Which variety do you prefer?			

Scenario 2

	Alternative 1	Alternative 2	Alternative 3
colour	Cream	Red	Opt out
taste	Sweet	Sweet	
texture	Elastic	Not elastic	
smell	Good	Not good	
size	Small	Big	
price	650	400	
Choice question: Which variety do you prefer?			

Scenario 3

	Alternative 1	Alternative 2	Alternative 3
colour	Cream	Red	Opt out
taste	Egegeti	Sweet	
texture	Not elastic	Elastic	
smell	Not good	Good	
size	Big	Small	
price	1,000	1,650	
Choice question: Which variety do you prefer?			

Scenario 4

	Alternative 1	Alternative 2	Alternative 3
colour	Red	Brown	Opt out
taste	Egegeti	Sweet	
texture	Elastic	Not elastic	
smell	Good	Good	
size	Big	Small	
price	400	650	
Choice question: Which variety do you prefer?			

Block 2

Scenario 1

	Alternative 1	Alternative 2	Alternative 3
colour	White	Brown	Opt out
taste	Bitter	Egegeti	
texture	Elastic	Not elastic	
smell	Good	Not good	
size	Small	Big	
price	1,000	1,000	
Choice question: Which variety do you prefer?			

Scenario 2

	Alternative 1	Alternative 2	Alternative 3
colour	Cream	White	Opt out
taste	Sweet	Egegeti	
texture	Not elastic	Not elastic	
smell	Good	Not good	
size	Small	Big	
price	400	1,650	
Choice question: Which variety do you prefer?			

Scenario 3

	Alternative 1	Alternative 2	Alternative 3
colour	Cream	Red	Opt out
taste	Bitter	Egegeti	
texture	Not elastic	Elastic	
smell	Not good	Good	
size	Small	Small	
price	1,000	400	
Choice question: Which variety do you prefer?			

Scenario 4

	Alternative 1	Alternative 2	Alternative 3
colour	White	Cream	Opt out
taste	Egegeti	Bitter	
texture	Not elastic	Elastic	
smell	Not good	Good	
size	Big	Big	
price	1,650	650	
Choice question: Which variety do you prefer?			

Block 3

Scenario 1

	Alternative 1	Alternative 2	Alternative 3
colour	Brown	Red	Opt out
taste	Sweet	Egegeti	
texture	Elastic	Elastic	
smell	Good	Good	
size	Big	Small	
price	400	650	
Choice question: Which variety do you prefer?			

Scenario 2

	Alternative 1	Alternative 2	Alternative 3
colour	Red	Cream	Opt out
taste	Sweet	Bitter	
texture	Elastic	Elastic	
smell	Good	Not good	
size	Big	Small	
price	1,650	650	
Choice question: Which variety do you prefer?			

Scenario 3

	Alternative 1	Alternative 2	Alternative 3
colour	Red	White	Opt out
taste	Sweet	Bitter	
texture	Elastic	Not Elastic	
smell	Not good	Good	
size	Big	Small	
price	650	1,000	
Choice question: Which variety do you prefer?			

Scenario 4

	Alternative 1	Alternative 2	Alternative 3
colour	White	Brown	Opt out
taste	Sweet	Egegeti	
texture	Not Elastic	Not Elastic	
smell	Good	Not good	
size	Small	Big	
price	400	1,650	
Choice question: Which variety do you prefer?			

Block 4

Scenario 1

	Alternative 1	Alternative 2	Alternative 3
colour	Cream	Red	Opt out
taste	Egegeti	Sweet	
texture	Not Elastic	Elastic	
smell	Not good	Good	
size	Small	Small	
price	1,000	1,650	
Choice question: Which variety do you prefer?			

Scenario 2

	Alternative 1	Alternative 2	Alternative 3
colour	Cream	White	Opt out
taste	Sweet	Egegeti	
texture	Elastic	Not Elastic	
smell	Good	Not good	
size	Big	Big	
price	400	1,650	
Choice question: Which variety do you prefer?			

Scenario 3

	Alternative 1	Alternative 2	Alternative 3
colour	Brown	White	Opt out
taste	Egegeti	Bitter	
texture	Not Elastic	Elastic	
smell	Not good	Good	
size	Small	Big	
price	1,650	650	
Choice question: Which variety do you prefer?			

Scenario 4

	Alternative 1	Alternative 2	Alternative 3
colour	White	Brown	Opt out
taste	Bitter	Egegeti	
texture	Elastic	Not Elastic	
smell	Good	Not good	
size	Small	Big	
price	650	1,650	
Choice question: Which variety do you prefer?			

Block 5

Scenario 1

	Alternative 1	Alternative 2	Alternative 3
colour	Brown	Cream	Opt out
taste	Egegeti	Bitter	
texture	Not Elastic	Elastic	
smell	Not good	Not good	
size	Small	Big	
price	1,650	1,000	
Choice question: Which variety do you prefer?			

Scenario 2

	Alternative 1	Alternative 2	Alternative 3
colour	Brown	Cream	Opt out
taste	Sweet	Bitter	
texture	Elastic	Not Elastic	
smell	Not good	Good	
size	Small	Big	
price	400	1,000	
Choice question: Which variety do you prefer?			

Scenario 3

	Alternative 1	Alternative 2	Alternative 3
colour	White	Brown	Opt out
taste	Bitter	Sweet	
texture	Elastic	Not Elastic	
smell	Not good	Good	
size	Small	Small	
price	1,000	400	
Choice question: Which variety do you prefer?			

Scenario 4

	Alternative 1	Alternative 2	Alternative 3
colour	White	Brown	Opt out
taste	Bitter	Egegeti	
texture	Elastic	Not Elastic	
smell	Good	Not good	
size	Small	Big	
price	650	1,650	
Choice question: Which variety do you prefer?			

Block 6

Scenario 1

	Alternative 1	Alternative 2	Alternative 3
colour	White	Cream	Opt pout
taste	Egegeti	Egegeti	
texture	Not Elastic	Not Elastic	
smell	Not good	Not good	
size	Big	Big	
price	1,650	1,000	
Choice question: Which variety do you prefer?			

Scenario 2

	Alternative 1	Alternative 2	Alternative 3
colour	Brown	Red	Opt out
taste	Bitter	Sweet	
texture	Elastic	Not Elastic	
smell	Good	Not good	
size	Big	Small	
price	650	400	
Choice question: Which variety do you prefer?			

Scenario 3

	Alternative 1	Alternative 2	Alternative 3
colour	Red	Cream	Opt out
taste	Bitter	Bitter	
texture	Not Elastic	Elastic	
smell	Good	Not good	
size	Big	Small	
price	650	1,000	
Choice question: Which variety do you prefer?			

Scenario 4

	Alternative 1	Alternative 2	Alternative 3
colour	Red	Brown	Opt out
taste	Bitter	Bitter	
texture	Not Elastic	Elastic	
smell	Good	Good	
size	Big	Small	
price	650	650	
Choice question: Which variety do you prefer?			

Appendix II. MNL output (Pooled Sample)

Normal exit: 5 iterations. Status=0, F= 488.2996

 Start values obtained using MNL model

Dependent variable Choice

Log likelihood function -488.29961

Estimation based on N = 480, K = 8

Inf.Cr.AIC = 992.6 AIC/N = 2.068

R2=1-LogL/LogL* Log-L fncn R-sqrd R2Adj

Constants only -489.0917 .0016-.0121

Response data are given as ind. choices

Number of obs.= 480, skipped 0 obs

CHOICE	Standard Coefficient	Prob. Error	z	95% Confidence Interval
BCOLORB	.43231**	.18356	2.36	.0185 .07254 .79209
BCOLORW	.43443**	.17574	2.47	.0134 .08998 .77888
BCOLORC	.39700**	.15583	2.55	.0108 .09158 .70241
BTASTE	-.38914***	.10615	-3.67	.0002 -.59719 -.18109
BTEXT	-.47138***	.14129	-3.34	.0008 -.74831 -.19445
BSMELL	-.46867***	.14792	-3.17	.0015 -.75859 -.17875
BSIZE	.39942***	.13464	2.97	.0030 .13553 .66331
BNPRICE	-.00070***	.00015	-4.63	.0000 -.00099 -.00040

 ***, **, * ==> Significance at 1%, 5%, 10% level.

Model was estimated on Jan 27, 2014 at 09:08:38 AM

Appendix III: Output for Hausman test for IID assumption

 Discrete choice (multinomial logit) model
 Dependent variable Choice
 Log likelihood function -160.50719
 Estimation based on N = 306, K = 8
 Inf.Cr.AIC = 337.0 AIC/N = 1.101
 R2=1-LogL/LogL* Log-L fncn R-sqrd R2Adj
 Constants only -174.7670 .0816 .0569
 Response data are given as ind. choices
 Number of obs.= 480, skipped 174 obs
Hausman test for IIA. Excluded choices are B
ChiSqrd[8] = 39.7764, Pr(C>c) = .0000

	Standard	Prob.	95% Confidence
CHOICE Coefficient	Error	z	z >Z* Interval
BCOLORB	1.61099***	.48722	3.31 .0009 .65606 2.56592
BCOLORW	1.00463***	.34030	2.95 .0032 .33766 1.67160
BCOLORC	2.49971***	.49212	5.08 .0000 1.53517 3.46425
BTASTE	-.40399*	.22680	-1.78 .0749 -.84851 .04053
BTEXT	-1.11872***	.30659	-3.65 .0003 -1.71962 -.51782
BSMELL	-.07918	.37405	-.21 .8324 -.81230 .65395
BSIZE	1.19916***	.31751	3.78 .0002 .57686 1.82146
BPRICE	.00026	.00040	.65 .5167 -.00053 .00105

 ***, **, * ==> Significance at 1%, 5%, 10% level.

Model was estimated on Sep 19, 2013 at 11:38:49 PM

Appendix IV: ML output (pooled sample)

Normal exit: 23 iterations. Status=0, F= 466.5887

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Random Parameters Logit Model
Dependent variable          CHOICE
Log likelihood function     -466.58866
Restricted log likelihood   -527.33390
Chi squared [ 13](P= .000)  121.49048
Significance level          .00000
McFadden Pseudo R-squared  .1151931
Estimation based on N =    480, K = 13
Inf.Cr.AIC =    959.2 AIC/N =    1.998
R2=1-LogL/LogL* Log-L fncn R-sqrd R2Adj
No coefficients -527.3339 .1152 .1030
Constants only -489.0917 .0460 .0329
At start values -494.1363 .0557 .0428
Response data are given as ind. choices
Replications for simulated probs. = 100
Used Halton sequences in simulations.
RPL model with panel has    120 groups
Fixed number of obsrvs./group=    4
Number of obs.=    480, skipped    0 obs
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CHOICE	Coefficient	Standard Error	z	Prob. z >Z*	95% Confidence Interval	

Random parameters in utility functions						
BCOLORB	.71487**	.28256	2.53	.0114	.16105	1.26868
BCOLORW	.82998***	.29162	2.85	.0044	.25842	1.40154
BCOLORC	.62461**	.26080	2.40	.0166	.11346	1.13577
BTAST	.55217*	.30155	1.83	.0671	-.03885	1.14320
BTEXT	.83548***	.24101	3.47	.0005	.36311	1.30785
BSMELL	1.09909***	.24232	4.54	.0000	.62415	1.57404
BFSIZE	.41537**	.20811	2.00	.0459	.00748	.82326
BPRIC	-.00076***	.00019	-4.09	.0000	-.00113	-.00040
Distns. of RPs. Std.Devs or limits of triangular						
NsBCOLOR	.95296***	.30163	3.16	.0016	.36178	1.54414
NsBCOLOR	.95296***	.30163	3.16	.0016	.36178	1.54414
NsBCOLOR	.95296***	.30163	3.16	.0016	.36178	1.54414
NsBTAST	1.90271***	.36548	5.21	.0000	1.18637	2.61904
NsBTEXT	.40945	.49708	.82	.4101	-.56481	1.38372
NsBSMELL	.98789***	.31719	3.11	.0018	.36621	1.60956
NsBFSIZE	.96320***	.34590	2.78	.0054	.28524	1.64116
CsBPRIC	0.0(Fixed Parameter).....				

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***, **, * ==> Significance at 1%, 5%, 10% level.
Fixed parameter ... is constrained to equal the value or had a nonpositive st.error because of an earlier problem.
Model was estimated on May 23, 2014 at 04:08:32 PM

Appendix V: Individual specific willingness to pay estimates for each attribute

Respondent	wcolb	wcolw	wcolc	wtaste	wtext	wsmell	wsize
1	1625.75	1434.75	94.1426	-457.798	913.088	1613.37	1020.58
2	1782.64	1009.19	269.226	1518.65	882.552	413.462	211.517
3	586.041	1449.04	764.526	2894.56	1100.73	1520.01	1157.99
4	1078.1	1813.64	1576.06	-827.771	1039.56	1086.91	31.7154
5	894.471	1477.63	938.9	-820.531	1230.05	567.644	57.699
6	775.777	1255.07	270.048	190.875	1314.98	2104.93	-588.984
7	735.307	1006.35	1469.39	-1270.64	1181.53	2263.14	-132.439
8	1780.77	888.971	-277.524	87.2286	880.158	797.409	993.192
9	1181.18	777.974	1032.3	1062.62	1166.75	2240.75	-162.52
10	1672.47	9.71875	428.551	-6.37132	979.687	1521.94	359.125
11	1630.01	1162.04	63.6562	-656.414	1070.77	312.5	-180.043
12	1935.18	210.31	988.689	1084.07	939.863	1097.88	676.195
13	556.074	1912.64	149.664	2285.88	999.614	1341.63	373.525
14	328.917	940.946	1433.29	-2592.09	1083.69	1234.56	-242.69
15	612.978	554.671	862.765	2174.11	1258.05	1571.62	1111.16
16	1365.55	650.703	475.537	1562.58	914.416	1633.53	-279.691
17	1069.98	-147.232	1456.24	295.4	1257.37	2376.94	438.957
18	854.491	932.28	1464.82	-1770.53	928.961	1276.8	1406.53
19	884.134	1117.88	-223.449	1693.02	927.359	711.099	1752.69
20	903.886	1487	792.354	-2216.26	921.971	1125.83	-117.013
21	412.698	1800.83	237.937	-1703.47	1122.57	1933	444.068
22	897.331	1579.75	454.452	1763.04	1269.18	2571.84	-81.2005
23	390.137	695.939	1017.16	-213.797	1298.88	2411.78	323.915
24	739.083	644.845	404.188	626.152	1131.34	2518.6	792.269
25	2.31222	1396.77	856.572	2950.77	1070.21	882.605	795.823
26	826.876	1591.64	667.041	-1888.72	1001.33	455.849	602.497
27	1428.29	1154.69	1164.56	1424.95	1067.53	1445.43	32.3642
28	1099.4	744.722	1194.89	1784.61	1045.81	1542	1246.45
29	684.267	940.945	1440.51	-1299.17	1151.11	2295.77	223.602
30	659.509	1458.3	986.95	-572.232	1249.08	2219.47	721.528
31	793.147	618.551	451.954	5.28215	1155.61	813.062	1081.21
32	316.193	1670.42	1082.96	-16.7906	1180.69	1488.03	266.515
33	1103.13	738.287	1179.98	1795.48	1052.81	1465.17	1233.49
34	667.303	1690.91	386.55	-212.903	1221.79	2183.32	-44.4202
35	-161.491	1206.29	702.421	389.504	1168.57	1033.54	698.062
36	1429.3	1089.18	675.127	3479.74	1242.48	1805.21	-555.946
37	1582.48	1401.03	45.7171	-1770.61	980.444	1636.01	976.745
38	1248.66	1253.91	997.051	-2047.01	1137.48	773.369	224.344
39	630.604	-179.634	1521.4	229.564	1166.79	2213.71	434.05
40	774.612	918.394	1448.04	-1361.5	1153.68	1461.95	351.315
41	461.205	1446.87	1374.38	-2142.28	1144.55	1354.77	723.334
42	453.19	509.602	1124.4	3186.93	1245.89	1908.13	452.751
43	358.916	1615.88	1318.82	-1960.34	1164.35	1290.53	766.919
44	444.697	617.298	1011.31	3335.91	1223.04	1884.18	428.284

45	274.06	887.594	1663.69	-1035.93	1057.76	1225.28	-747.137
46	196.973	1686.1	1206.5	1044.02	1248.36	1060.61	706.509
47	587.697	1082.31	1162.22	4226.31	722.07	276.063	313.575
48	853.988	403.791	717.136	137.963	794.686	2071.59	1888.33
49	607.56	472.79	1122.73	1728.42	1135.27	1764.89	625.444
50	1758.93	760.064	740.781	360.52	885.111	1078	722.315
51	491.234	1936.5	869.224	-2040.68	1057.83	865.387	751.249
52	618.47	859.296	1287.85	3830.53	1256.85	1718.85	228.493
53	649.219	1780.02	816.04	2594.49	1123.39	1343.96	1228.74
54	863.963	1687.91	714.554	2982.38	1087.99	1096.85	310.842
55	50.8153	1897.83	-200.365	183.755	1155	638.089	1427.77
56	1420.84	1868.21	-253.443	1729.7	791.16	100.638	104.902
57	583.266	1192.84	1076.7	4279.88	667.557	334.512	231.619
58	613.718	1111.38	260.005	3611.65	1058.31	1074.72	-269.812
59	674.925	220.922	810.097	1758.98	1139.32	1970.82	-298.845
60	711.256	1018.45	290.25	3559.05	1326.47	1941.98	-468.432
61	1327.7	894.492	1238.97	1455.81	1051.85	1650.94	1372.94
62	692.416	1575.03	971.041	2550.58	1203.24	1135.6	1205.88
63	1638.18	685.852	939.666	1878.61	975.761	501.785	1222.75
64	218.482	1631.68	1063.34	-126.167	1254.43	1417.69	388.291
65	863.952	1891.83	978.801	740.595	882.183	1652.56	163.296
66	1478.21	817.04	537.265	3640.41	1237.79	1813.47	-71.2562
67	2449.25	807.073	322.364	1668.83	946.297	853.765	665.75
68	249.149	471.477	1480.17	2606.29	856.927	426.254	709.978
69	594.688	605.112	649.845	3421.83	1022.13	939.033	-206.56
70	397.301	1585.74	1651.75	-962.87	1108.34	1003.06	865.719
71	1600.55	634.658	619.092	272.528	781.894	827.041	715.547
72	280.827	62.5039	1796.62	701.473	1040.62	1509.62	230.225
73	735.278	493.915	1012.21	3131.71	1309.64	2148.66	177.504
74	1286.37	622.899	612.741	2098.61	1014.87	631.876	1535.89
75	1635.24	1192.42	1062.55	300.814	1203.71	1245.39	278.652
76	791.8	516.632	1005.79	3082.52	1308.06	2208.4	160.127
77	648.544	918.16	1544.49	-1336.2	1159.43	2158.19	309.204
78	551.008	165.007	1499.91	-964.031	1105.33	2112.43	428.232
79	1050.09	566.556	802.805	2398.06	1289.86	2497.72	574.975
80	665.462	969.07	979.369	518.076	1370.48	138.073	334.083
81	1735.18	779.864	609.683	1273.21	1191.71	2238.59	187.195
82	614.093	1406.02	1105.64	-383.01	1236.15	2281.74	884.085
83	1904.87	826.359	609.362	1238.59	1170.89	2075.25	79.662
84	254.249	1611.26	1115.69	-295.307	1204.18	1474.19	377.609
85	1615.35	1341.19	444.078	-695.307	810.951	271.783	1310.93
86	1336.21	1729.7	-321.349	1450.25	811.092	200.411	97.305
87	856.186	583.932	758.38	258.173	923.922	1899.29	1910.14
88	1540.65	715.731	415.277	-510.348	1123.27	2494.07	877.789
89	649.055	1668.37	823.169	2254.51	1124.52	1348.57	1197.89
90	2038.26	473.737	311.908	1036.43	891.96	714.078	45.5594

91	471.996	2174.65	6.18981	-264.31	1031.42	1389.24	899.315
92	611.153	1551.57	491.823	-1618.9	1086.07	1764.77	919.452
93	2157.47	1226.07	681.403	-99.4047	789.849	1315.35	-325.18
94	2709.55	925.44	89.2735	1697.78	880.222	447.521	386.918
95	1425.63	744.472	552.935	2004.29	1075.95	754.619	1533.1
96	924.734	830.538	1390.7	-1506.05	1083.54	2105.29	309.507
97	1356.73	1897.04	478.576	894.766	1055.95	1387.66	-342.568
98	1991.45	1185.87	346.414	282.036	909.509	901.024	-423.539
99	788.636	1560.31	891.623	-518.531	1306.8	359.397	401.581
100	1446.75	733.686	543.059	1985.33	1079.11	728.875	1508.91
101	815.007	938.358	1436.95	-1607.56	1036.25	2306.22	257.14
102	2120.96	920.424	1113.52	216.468	883.423	1509.71	175.658
103	-18.776	2046.9	637.004	-345.025	1199.73	-70.2725	1827.61
104	1075.15	302.65	1202.61	3639.97	1125.1	2032.6	-303.376
105	873.487	1558.73	558.133	2580.4	1052.47	1141.98	296.929
106	649.633	440.823	1026.83	3329.27	1211.21	2195.04	48.4997
107	382.644	1426.23	1341.04	-1953.84	1104.83	1357.05	866.104
108	444.638	744.815	1171.03	4151.89	713.62	117.08	357.164
109	649.372	619.39	188.752	-111.711	1067.46	2353.05	1490.54
110	755.6	1690.21	838.811	2303.64	1151.28	1501.99	1198.12
111	571.423	1404.04	984.21	-411.894	1189.31	2266.81	817.665
112	1192.82	1592.46	754.824	1990.82	1028.39	1369.85	70.6801
113	1006.07	659.951	104.804	1590.51	992.582	676.592	1932.99
114	651.151	615.736	196.346	-143.262	1068.03	2366.82	1460.95
115	609.361	1399.96	981.209	-425.823	1184.93	2340.39	743.647
116	734.868	1680.79	828.333	2311.44	1152.21	1487.21	1219.5
117	1975.08	1400.32	1061.11	-1224.59	728.352	2580	24.5433
118	955.013	859.83	1248.47	-1899.64	1094.74	1852.71	-39.2309
119	630.789	2183.62	217.522	-148.638	1108.51	1521.28	937.502
120	290.648	1134.25	102.393	-1517.85	849.278	1436.31	1685.91

Appendix VI: MNL output for prior coefficients used to generate a Bayesian efficient design

Normal exit from iterations. Exit status=0.

```

+-----+
| Multinomial Logit Model          |
| Maximum Likelihood Estimates     |
| Model estimated: Jun 01, 2013 at 10:10:14AM. |
| Dependent variable      CHOICE  |
| Weighting variable      None   |
| Number of observations    480   |
| Iterations completed      4    |
| Log likelihood function  -319.2797 |
| Restricted log likelihood -332.7106 |
| Chi squared              26.86191 |
| Degrees of freedom        7     |
| Prob[ChiSqd > value] =   .3528985E-03 |
| Corrected for Choice Based Sampling |
| Hosmer-Lemeshow chi-squared = 14.23128 |
| P-value= .07593 with deg.fr. =  8   |
+-----+
+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+
| Variable | Coefficient | Standard Error | b/St.Er. | P[|Z|>z] | Mean of X |
+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+
          Characteristics in numerator of Prob[Y = 1]
COLORB   -.49463208   .26589934   -1.860   .0629   .25000000
COLORW   -.66541965   .26409825   -2.520   .0117   .25000000
COLORC   -1.00611845   .27519042   -3.656   .0003   .25208333
TASTE    -.11374610   .11370014   -1.000   .3171   1.00000000
TEXT     -.24490113   .18806460   -1.302   .1928   .50208333
SMELL    -.53963005   .18912871   -2.853   .0043   .50000000
SIZE     .20161917   .18762537   1.075   .2826   .50625000
LOGPRICE .32052514   .09987532   3.209   .0013   2.90835414

```